

Postulating ‘Ethnography of Enculturation’: A high-level overview of various social science research techniques that can be used to study human enculturation processes

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Abstract

We had first introduced the concept of “Ethnography of enculturation” in our paper on generic identity theory. We had also published two other papers on ethnography, the gist of which can be understood to enhance the readership experience of this paper. This is however, not mandatory. We believe the “Ethnography of enculturation” would constitute a very important concept and component of twenty-first century social sciences since it would give us an insight and understanding into how humans are enculturated (or acculturated) as the case may be, and how their identities are shaped in the real-world. Ethnography is a very important qualitative social science research technique, and encompasses not just participant observation, but also the use of interviews the use of questionnaires, focus group discussions, surveys, literature review, and case studies, but also novel techniques such as netnography, and fieldwork from a distance. It also makes use of technology and audio-visual aids as necessary. In any topic such as this, ethics would be of paramount importance, and this topic is discussed as well. This paper must also be understood in relation to our papers on genetic identity and extended identity, and all these papers are inter-linked in a continuous chain. This paper could also provide us with a research mechanism to better help us understand real-world excesses like the rise of terrorism, and deviant and aberrant behavior. It would therefore not only be an important cog in the wheel in our mission of the “globalization of science”, but would also amplify the utility of social science research techniques in addressing real-world issues and concerns.

Introduction

We had first introduced the concept of “Ethnography of enculturation” in our paper on generic identity theory, which was published in the autumn of 2019, and had revisited it in our paper on extended identity theory as. We had also published two other papers on ethnography, the gist of which can be understood to enhance the readership experience of this paper. This is however, not mandatory, and this paper can be readily understood without reading those two papers as well. We believe the “Ethnography of enculturation” would constitute a very important concept and component of twenty-first century social sciences since it would give us an insight and understanding into how humans are enculturated (or acculturated) as the case may be, and how their identities are shaped in the real-world, by an interaction of different types of processes. The processes presented and attempted to be studied as a part of this paper would be entirely cultural in nature; physical and biological growth and development would be an entirely different topic of study. However, a study of physical growth and mental growth patterns would be a useful adjunct to such studies, and any ethnographer must possess a working knowledge of biological growth patterns as well. Ethnography is a very important qualitative social science research technique, and encompasses not just participant observation, but also the use of interviews the use of questionnaires, focus group discussions, surveys, literature review and case studies, but also novel techniques such as netnography, and fieldwork from a distance. It also makes use of technology and audio-visual aids as necessary. In any issue such as this, ethics would be of paramount importance, and this topic is discussed as well in a fair level of detail. Notably, the “Ethnography of enculturation” can be readily accomplished both for individuals as well as for groups to elicit patterns, and this would endow it with an added utility. It can also be productively, gainfully and fruitfully be employed to study both living and dead people, though the methods of research may vary.

This paper must also be understood in relation to our papers on genetic identity and extended identity, and all these papers are inter-linked in a continuous chain. This paper could also provide us with a research mechanism to better help us understand real-world excesses like the rise of terrorism, and undesirable, deviant and aberrant behavior. It would therefore not only be an important cog in the wheel in our mission of the “globalization of science”, but would also amplify the utility of social science research techniques in addressing real-world issues and concerns. This may also be necessary given that many paradigms in social sciences research appear to be outdated, and also appear to be inadequate to handle post-globalized scenarios. This paper, like all our earlier papers, is also based on the concept of the “psychic unity of mankind” which states that deep inside, all humans and individuals have the same mental and emotional makeup, and humans can indeed live in harmony with each other, cultural differences notwithstanding provided mechanisms to make this happen are put in place.

We also take a culture neutral stance and lay bare the concepts so that anyone without an exposure to multiple cultures can understand the concepts easily. Many people may have Amar Chitra Katha type “Muslims as invaders” and may miss the bus completely; they may not understand that deep inside, all humans are the same. Humans come in different hues and with different mental make ups even within the same culture or community; in this connection the term “petting zoo” would come in handy. This term was first used by Christine Fair. However, many individuals even today are enculturated completely differently even today, and this is deeply disturbing. For examples, many Muslims even more educated

ones support terrorism or outdated cultural concepts such as polygamy or triple talaq. We must distinguish between the two entirely different concepts and chalk out a path for remediation. We must therefore phase out legacy social science research paradigms many of which were designed to satisfy European curiosities regarding the rest of the exotic and unexplored world to modern inter-disciplinary and cross-cultural approaches that are designed to solve twenty-first century real-world problems.

The earliest evidence of the study of human development and the use of some form of “ethnographic” techniques, dates back to the year 1787, when a journal in Germany published the German philosopher Dietrich Tiedemann’s observation of his son’s sensory, and cognitive development patterns over his first two and half years. This was similar to “baby biographies” being recorded and maintained by several researchers at that time. Later, in the year 1877, the famous English naturalist Charles Darwin published very detailed notes on his son Doddy’s sensory, cognitive and emotional development processes over his first twelve months. In the early 1900’s G. Stanley Hall, undertook systematic studies of child development and senescence as well. In this paper, we however attempt to take the idea of the “Ethnography of enculturation” to altogether new level by drawing on our observations made in our already published papers. This approach can also be extended to both linguistic enculturation and linguistic acculturation, and this would as such constitute a useful extension of this type of study. These must be naturally be understood against the backdrop of the science of language dynamics; we have published three papers on this topic; language or linguistic ideologies must also be understood and vetted against these concepts. For example, upper middle class Indians or the English-literate elite may have a pro-English ideology, while rural folk in the Hindi heartland may have a strong anti-English mindset.

The meaning of “Ethnography”

We had introduced the concept of ethnography of enculturation in our paper on generic identity theory, but it is now time to explore this concept in a little greater detail. We had also published two other papers on Ethnography, and had discussed what ethnography was. Let us not recapitulate this topic for the benefit of our readers. The term “Ethnography” is a combination of two Greek words: namely “ethnos” which means folk or peoples, and “grapho” which means to write. The term was however first introduced in popular parlance by Johann Friedrich Schopperlin and the German variant was introduced by A F Thilo in 1767. August Ludwig von Schlozer later introduced this term into academia, though in a historical context, and the usage of the term eventually became widespread. Ethnography is defined as the systematic, first-hand, structured and qualitative study of different types of peoples and cultures, particularly less developed ones, or quaint and exotic ones. It is also referred to as a “portrait of peoples”. It has canonically implied the study of “primitive” people by “advanced” people, though this connotation which began during the age of exploration and colonialism, is outdated in our view, and must change.¹

¹ Krebs, Robert E. (2004). Groundbreaking Scientific Experiments, Inventions, and Discoveries of the Middle Ages and the Renaissance

Over the years, Ethnography has developed and evolved to encompass all types of cultures in its realm, and this includes even urban cultures and landscapes, and cultures that are in geographical proximity to the ethnographer's place of residence. The ethnographer may observe subjects in a process known as "participant observation", and this usually takes place at the subject's residence. Fieldwork is central to ethnography, and the field is referred to as the laboratory of the anthropologist or the ethnographer. Thus, the ethnographer interacts with the subjects over a prolonged period in time, and understands all aspects of their culture or behavior. He also collects as much information about the subjects as possible either before the field visit, or during the field visit. He also interacts with or interviews as many people as possible within the boundaries of that group. The subject may be explored either through the point of view of the ethnographer (etic approaches), or the point of view of the subject (emic approaches). Ethnography is therefore, one of the most important qualitative techniques in social sciences research. In addition to participant observation techniques, interviews and group discussions may also be used. This study involves the use of aids such as pencil, paper, video camera, tape recorder etc, and results in the final generation of a written report which is the output of the ethnographic study. Often genealogy and pedigree analysis is also done. The use of ethnography and participant observation the way we know it today is attributed to Bronislaw Malinowski who published his seminal "Argonauts of the Western Pacific" in relation to the Trobriand Islanders in 1922. However, other expeditions such as the Second Kamchatka expedition of 1733 to 1743 and the expedition to the Torres Straits were made much earlier. Notably, Franz Boas also contributed a great deal to ethnography. ^{2 3}

Ethnography is particularly useful in exploring diverse cultural phenomena where the researcher observes society at close quarters and first hand. It is also particularly useful in discovering the nuances and intricacies of group behavior, group interactions, and social inter-relationships, and the underlying causes of such behaviour. It can also help discover group norms, etiquette, social institutions such as family, kinship and marriage, other socio-cultural phenomena, and can help discover underlying factors behind manifested behavior. It can also help explore qualitative and intangible aspects of a culture in a way that quantitative research techniques cannot. This type of research techniques is also often used in conjunction with ethnomethodology (also referred to as the methodology of people) which is a study of how social order is produced through different processes of social interaction.. Ethnography replaced arm-chair anthropology which was popular a couple of centuries ago, and is being increasingly used in diverse fields of the social sciences besides anthropology where this technique was birthed. Some form of ethnography was also used by Herodotus and Tacitus in ancient times, and in various writings about the Egyptians, Scythians, and the Germanic tribes as well. Marco Polo and Ibn Battuta also travelled to ancient lands. Ethnography is however time consuming taking upto a full year or more for a high-quality report to be generated, and requires a well-trained researcher. Protracted, prolonged and extensive fieldwork is also necessary to avoid hasty generalizations and erroneous conclusions being reached. Additionally, It also often takes time to build trust with participants and respondents in such a way that a meaningful dialogue is established. (Launay 1980)

² Being Ethnographic: A guide to the theory and practice of Ethnography Raymond Madden Second Edition

³ Cultural Anthropology: Appreciating Cultural Diversity Fifteenth Edition Conrad Phillip Kottak McGraw Hill, 2013

Many different definitions have been attempted for the term Ethnography. Ethnography is often defined as follows: “Ethnography refers to a systematic study of different kinds of peoples and cultures. It is therefore the study of people in their naturally occurring settings or ‘fields’ through the use of methods which capture their social meanings and ordinary activities, always involving the researcher participating directly in the setting, and also their activities, in order to collect data in a systematic manner but without meaning being imposed on them externally.” In the words of Anthropologists Alan Bernard and Jonathan Spencer (Spencer 1996), the word Ethnography has two meanings namely, “Ethnography as product” (or Ethnographic writings) and “Ethnography as process” (or Participant observation and fieldwork), with the former being derived from the latter. Martyn Hammersley and Paul Atkinson state in 2007, “Ethnography typically involves the Ethnographer participating either overtly or covertly in people’s daily lives for an extended period of time, carefully observing what happens, listening to what is said, and asking questions (either through formal and informal interviews), collecting documents, materials and artifacts, and in fact, collecting whatever other data or information is available, to throw light on the issues that are the emerging focus of enquiry.” (Gupta and Ferguson 1997). According to another definition provided by Agar, “Ethnography is a very ambiguous and an amorphous term, but represents and encompasses both a process and a product. It combines various descriptive and analytical elements as well.” (Agar 1980)

All these definitions underline the importance of the process of careful and meticulous research and study, as well as the research report in communicating the findings of the study to different types of audiences. It also encompasses the process of knowledge-building and knowledge generation with regard to the group or community that is being studied. In the view of Wolcott and others, Knowledge building is a very important part of Ethnographic output, and the output of any study is used for further downstream analysis. Ethnography is also central to Anthropological studies. Michael Jackson states in this regard, “For Anthropology, Ethnography remains vital, not because Ethnographic methods guarantee certain knowledge of others, but because Ethnographic fieldwork brings us into direct dialogue with others.” Ethnography is widely used nowadays, and different schools of ethnography such as the British school and the Chicago school have emerged. ^{4 5}

In 2018, we had authored a paper named “Presenting the ‘Structured and Annotated Participant-driven Appraisal’ technique in Ethnography: Towards the universal realization of multi-vocality in ethnographic studies”, where we had developed concepts to minimize cross-cultural bias in ethnographic studies through a method known as annotation. Another paper, “Introducing Long-term Ethnography: Positioning Long-term Ethnography as a valuable tool for long-term Ethnographic research” would also be useful. We had also authored a paper named “Operationalizing cross-cultural research design: Practical, cost-effective, and a minimalistic application of cross-cultural research design to minimize cultural bias in research and reconcile diverse viewpoints.” The principles and concepts developed in all

⁴ Introducing Long-term Ethnography: Positioning Long-term Ethnography as a valuable tool for longterm Ethnographic research Published in IJISRT Volume 7 Issue 7 July 2022 Sujay Rao Mandavilli

⁵ Presenting the ‘Structured and Annotated Participantdriven Appraisal’ technique in Ethnography: Towards the universal realization of Multivocality in Ethnographic studies Sujay Rao Mandavilli ELK’s International Journal of Social Science Vol 4, Number 4, 2018

these papers may also be borne in mind for the purposes of this paper. We had also published two papers on identity theory, namely generic identity theory and extended identity theory, (in 2019 and 2023 respectively) where we had also formulated the concept of identity modeling. These papers were published as “Generic Identity Theory for the Twenty-first Century: Towards grand unified approaches in identity formation, identity transformation and identity dilution or neutralization” and “Formulating ‘Extended identity theory’ for twenty-first century social sciences research: Modeling extended identity in relation to real-world observations and data.”

This paper takes concepts proposed in those papers to the next logical level, and is poised to become a milestone in twenty-first century social science. Anyone can therefore understand that no one is inherently good or bad (biological identity shapes individuals to a relatively small degree); cultural factors encompassing the totality of religion, language, myth, folklore, customs etc make all the difference. Thus, individuals do get radicalized, and radicalization as in particular been observed among Muslim youth; this is indeed a cause for concern, and anthropologists and ethnographers must get to the bottom of this. However, most social science research techniques and methods are not even geared to solving pressing real-world problems. This is the sad state of affairs that prevails today.^{6 7}

Participant observation method

Participant observation is one of the different types of data collection techniques used by ethnographers in qualitative research and ethnography. The concept "participant observation" was first coined by Eduard C. Lindeman in 1924 who was an American pioneer in adult education. It was identified as a fieldwork technique by the American anthropologist and social theorist Clyde Kluckhohn in 1940, The participant observation method, which is the principal method of ethnographic research, is when a an ethnographer socially becomes a part of the group they are studying in order to collect data and understand a social phenomenon or problem from close quarters, and as understood and experienced by the group being studied. The ethnographer partakes in all the life activities of the group under study. Often, he also establishes his residence near the subject's natural environment or setting. He might also invite some of the locals to his temporary residence. Thus, a variant of participant observation known as verandah anthropology was also practiced. This stands in marked contrast to non-participant Observations where there is a lack of participation by the observer in the life of the group. Participant observation also involves establishing rapport with the members of the group before the study can be commenced, and the results recorded, and this is often the most challenging part of an ethnographic exercise.

Thus, according to Howell (Howell 1972), the important phases of participant observation are establishing a rapport, intermingling with the locals and talking, acting and behaving like the locals do, recording observations, collecting and analyzing data, and performing the final analysis. He may also

⁶ Generic Identity Theory for the Twenty-first Century: Towards grand unified approaches in identity formation, identity transformation and identity dilution or neutralization Sujay Rao Mandavilli Elk Asia Pacific Journal of Social Sciences Volume 5, Issue 3, 2019

⁷ Formulating ‘Extended identity theory’ for twenty-first century social sciences research: Modeling extended identity in relation to real-world observations and data Sujay Rao Mandavilli IJISRT, July 2023

thus participate as a marginal native. The researcher often makes sure that their behaviour is not affected by his own presence, though this is often by no means easy. Participation in the lives of the locals and involvement in their activities could therefore be complete or partial, or various degrees in between and this would vary based on the study. As a part of ethnographic studies interviewing and group discussions must be adopted. Classroom sessions and questionnaires may also be adopted, but these may not be practical for all situations and contexts. There is also an interesting conflict arising from his own cultural biases and prejudices and the biases he may assimilate from the culture he is involved in; this is also something he needs to guard against. Sometimes, feedback from participants is sought to mitigate any bias and any misunderstanding. Investigator triangulation is also often adopted, and the investigators are changed during the course of the study to minimize bias. Fieldwork from a distance, or distance field work is also sometimes used in Anthropology. This approach was famously used in studying Japanese during the Second World War. Of late, netnography or ethnography on the internet has taken off, though ethical issues remain.^{8 9 10 11}

What is enculturation?

The ideas of identity formation and individuation are also tightly bound to the process of enculturation which occurs in every culture or society on earth, though probably in different ways. Enculturation is usually defined as the acquisition, (particularly during childhood and adolescence) of the prevailing characteristics, ideals and norms of a culture which help him understand the dynamics and workings of that culture, and become immersed in it. The culture in question here is the culture which he is birthed and raised in. In some cases, the individual may be exposed to a different macro culture in his childhood, and he acquires the norms and values of that society through a process known as acculturation, which is opposed to enculturation. Many different definitions have been attempted for the term enculturation.

According to a definition provided by the American Anthropologist Conrad Phillip Kottak in his book "Window on Humanity: concise introduction to Anthropology", "Enculturation refers to that process where the culture that is currently established teaches an individual the accepted norms of the culture or society where the individual lives or resides. The individual can become an accepted member, and fulfill the needs, functions, the roles and responsibilities of the group, and learns what type of behaviour is acceptable in the group. The individual also learns and becomes aware of the contexts of boundaries and accepted behaviour that dictates what is acceptable and not acceptable within the framework of the society. He also learns the traditional contexts and boundaries of that culture, and what type of behavior constitutes transgression. It teaches the individual about their roles and responsibilities within society as well as the accepted behavioural norms within that society." (Kottak 2004)¹²

⁸ Ethnography: Step by step Third Edition David M. Fettermann Sage Publications, 2010

⁹ Ethnographic Methods, Second Edition, Karl O'Reilly, Routledge, 2012

¹⁰ Ethnography: Principles in practice 3rd Edition, Paul Atkinson and Martyn Hammersley Routledge, 2007

¹¹ DeWalt, K. M., B. R. DeWalt, and C. B. Wayland. 1998. "Participant Observation." Pp. 259–99 in Handbook of Methods in Cultural Anthropology, edited by H. R. Bernard. Walnut Creek, Calif.: AltaMira Press.

¹² *Mirror for Humanity: A Concise Introduction to Cultural Anthropology* (McGraw-Hill, 2013 15th Edition) (ISBN 0078035015)

According to American Anthropologist E. Adamson Hoebel “enculturation is both a conscious and an unconscious conditioning process through which a man or a woman, both as a child or as an adult, achieves competence, skill and fitness in his culture, internalizes his culture and becomes thoroughly and completely internalized and enculturated in that culture.” In the worlds of the famous Anthropologist Margaret Mead, “enculturation is a process that is distinct from socialization in that enculturation refers to the actual process of cultural learning with a specific culture takes place, and the individual internalizes the dreams, aspirations and expectations, the rules, norms and requirements not just for the larger society taken as a whole, but also for every specific demand within that whole”.

Therefore, the process of enculturation teaches the citizens of a society how to function as responsible members of that society, and also know and become aware of what is expected of them and to discharge all their duties and responsibilities towards the state and society with great diligence. It also teaches individuals about the norms and established canons of that society. Most theories also state that cultural transmission is the means through which the process of enculturation takes place, and this is a largely subconscious or unconscious process of internalization that shapes and forms an individual’s attitudes, identity and behaviour. Several theories of enculturation have been proposed, examples being Bandura’s social learning theory and social cognitive theory which are based on an earlier “Social learning and imitation theory” developed by the American psychologist Neal E. Miller, another American psychologist John Dollard and others, and conclude that learning typically takes place in social and cultural contexts. A society also often possesses various institutions to aid in the process of enculturation, and check and punish deviant behavior. The process of behavior begins from birth, and continues till an individual dies. Linguistic enculturation refers to the process by which an individual acquires language and linguistic capability from his childhood in his native context and surroundings. This process begins with language acquisition within the context of the immediate family, and then proceeds to formal acquisition of language in much more formal contexts. This approach can also be used to study some or all aspects of the culture. For example, we can even have specialized variants such as the “Ethnography of education”, to observe learning processes and outcomes first-hand. It can even be used to investigate how human relationships are formed, and how humans interact with one another. It can also be used to research group dynamics.^{13 14}

What is acculturation?

The term “acculturation” refers to the changes that occur when different cultural groups come into the direct and intensive contact with one another. Acculturation is a dynamic and multi-dimensional process of adaptation that occurs when two or more distinct cultures come into sustained and direct contact with each other. The process of acculturation often involves different degrees culture learning, adoption, adaptation and maintenance that are contingent upon different cultural factors such as individual, group, and environmental factors. Acculturation is also a highly dynamic process because it is a continuous, integrated, interactional and fluctuating process; it is also multi-dimensional because it

¹³ Hoebel, Adamson E. (1954). *The Law of Primitive Man*. Harvard, Massachusetts: Atheneum.

¹⁴ Robert L. Winzeler, *Anthropology and Religion: What We Know, Think, and Question*, Altmira Press, Lanham, USA, 2012

takes place across numerous components of culture, and can result in multiple neo-cultural outcomes. The title “ethnography of enculturation” also naturally includes the “ethnography of acculturation”, though it is not highlighted in the title or moniker for the sake of ease or convenience. In case of the latter, acculturation patterns may be formally studied across individuals, cultures and societies. This would naturally be a very useful extension of this concept, with far-reaching consequences for ethnographic research.

The earliest definition of acculturation is attributed to the anthropologists Redfield, Linton, and Herskovits in the year 1936: Their definition reads, “Acculturation comprehends those phenomena which result when groups of individuals having different cultures come into continuous first-hand contact, with subsequent changes in the original culture patterns of either or both groups”. The Social Science Research Council however defines acculturation as follows: “Culture change that change which is initiated by the conjunction of two or more autonomous cultural systems. Its dynamics can be seen as the selective adaptation of value systems, the processes of integration and differentiation, the generation of developmental sequences, and the operation of role determinants and personality factors”.

Acculturation is commonly understood and taken to mean a continuous, symbiotic and bi-directional process where both cultures namely the immigrant’s culture and the host culture that are in continuous contact with one another can change to produce completely new equations over a period in time. Often many immigrant cultures interact with each other as well as with the host culture to produce new paradigms. It encompasses not only cultural, but social and psychological changes as well. However, it is usually the immigrant’s culture that changes the most, given that migrants are usually small in number to the total population. In case the immigrants are large in number, the host culture can also change substantially and significantly. Feeble (or marginal) cultures may also change more rapidly than robust ones, but this is by no means a hard and fast rule. In many cases, we do not yet know the eventual outcomes of acculturation; cultures like the USA are a melting pot and a synthesis of cultures, and immigration there is an ongoing process. The process of acculturation would also be determined based on whether the host culture is assimilating, accommodating or not, and characteristics of the host cultures can determine patterns of acculturation in the same manner as the cultural makeup of immigrants does. The process of acculturation has been formally studied since 1918, and more than one hundred definitions of the term have been put forward over the years.

As Y. Y Kim who studied assimilation patterns of immigrants in detail states,: “The acculturation process, therefore, is an interactive and continuous process that evolves in, and through the communication of an immigrant with the new socio-cultural milieu or environment. The acquired communication competence, in turn, reflects the degree or extent of that immigrant’s acculturation.” (Kim 1982) Thus, acculturation leads to a modification of cultures, and a healthy or a novel amalgam through cultural diffusion, a process which may manifest itself in many different contexts. This process is also sometimes known as transculturation (This term was coined by the Cuban anthropologist and historian Fernando Ortiz in 1940), and may sometimes lead to partial ethno-convergence (or pan-mixing) and also achieve some degree of homogenization, although this process has its obvious limits. Differences and paradoxes are bound to persist into eternity, as religious and linguistic differences can seldom die out completely;

this was proposed by us in our two papers on “the Symbiotic approach to socio-cultural change”, and as was strongly argued by the Canadian author and scholar Michael Ignatieff and others. The term acculturation can be used to describe language learning too, and the process of second-language acquisition has now become a highly formal field of study. Thus, the process of linguistic acculturation can be studied in diverse contexts and situations, and can be used to complement the “Ethnography of acculturation.”

What is transculturation?

The term “transculturation” is a term coined by Cuban anthropologist and historian Fernando Ortiz in 1940 (It is also sometimes traced to Jose Marti) to describe the concept and idea of the merging and converging cultures. He proposed the term in contrast to the much more commonly used terminology “acculturation”, which describes the process of changes in culture due to continuous and sustained contact. Transculturation on the other hand, is a process of cultural transformation marked by the influx of new cultural elements and the loss or significant alteration or transformation of existing cultural elements. Transculturation, therefore refers to the encounter between or among two or more cultures in which each culture acquires or adapts one or more elements of the other culture or cultures, and in which new elements of culture are created through a syncretic process of adaptation and mutual adjustment. This concept was first proposed by Ortiz to study certain phenomena in Cuban culture, but has found widespread use since.

The concepts of “successful transculturation” and “failed transculturation” are also sometimes used to refer to the results of a process of transculturation; these also arose in a Cuban context. Sometimes the emergence of new cultural phenomena is also referred to neo-culturation, though this is somewhat rare. Another term de-culturation refers to the loss of one’s own cultural identity, usually to a significant degree. We had also introduced the term co-enculturation in another paper; this would refer to co-enculturation in the same geographical context, but involves multiple cultures. The term transculturation makes more sense in globalized scenarios, but merger and synthesis of cultures would naturally have their limits; individual cultures would always prevail to some degree. Some cultures may also invariably and inevitably prove to be more dominant than some others; this is due to cultural hegemony. We had also proposed a symbiotic approach towards socio-cultural change in two of our earlier papers, and this process was referred to as “Proactive-interactive-symbiotic approach to long-term cultural change”. These papers would no doubt be a useful read. Convergence theorists also hold that cultures will gradually converge, though there would be natural limits to a convergence.^{15 16}

What is massculturation?

We had proposed the term “massculturation” in a paper that we published earlier this year. This term was formed as a portmanteau of two words, namely “mass” and “enculturation”. Massculturation is

¹⁵ The relevance of Culture and Personality Studies, National Character Studies, Cultural Determinism and Cultural Diffusion in Twenty-first Century Anthropology: An assessment of their compatibility with Symbiotic models of Socio-cultural change ELK Asia Pacific Journal of Social Science Volume 4, Issue 2, 2018 Sujay Rao Mandavilli

¹⁶ Articulating comprehensive frameworks on socio-cultural change: Perceptions of social and cultural change in contemporary Twenty-first century Anthropology from a ‘Neo-centrist’ perspective Published in ELK Asia Pacific Journal of Social Sciences Volume 3, Number 4 (July 2017 – September 2017) Sujay Rao Mandavilli

very much a reality nowadays, and has become widespread after the arrival of the mass media. Mass media refers to technology that is intended to reach a mass audience, and the vast majority of the public. It encompasses a diverse array of media all of which reach a large audience via processes of mass communication. The most common platforms for mass media are newspapers, magazines, radio, television, and the Internet. The invention of the printing press by Gutenberg paved the way for mass communication, and led to an intellectual revolution of sorts. The German-language “Relation aller Fürnemmen und gedenckwürdigen Historien”, which began publication in 1605 is commonly accepted to have been the first newspaper. The Oxford Gazette of 1665 was the world’s first English newspaper.

The first radio message was sent by Guglielmo Marconi in 1897, but commercial radio broadcasts became widespread by the early 1920’s. Millions of American homes had radios by the end of that decade. Silent films took off in the early 1900’s, and Hollywood was born. Sound arrived in films by the end of the 1920’s. John Logie Baird developed the first television in 1926, and an experimental broadcast was made by Herbert E. Ives and Frank Gray of Bell Telephone Laboratories in 1927. The Berlin Olympics of 1936 were telecast when few people owned a television. The first practical televisions dated to 1939, and the popularity of television soared in the 1950’s, with colour television becoming the norm by the 1960’s. In 1861 Philipp Reis developed the first telephone, which is today called the Reis telephone. Alexander Graham Bell was granted the first U.S. patent for the invention of the telephone in the year 1876. The world’s first commercial telephone services began in the 1880’s with the establishment of the earliest telephone exchanges.

The personal computer revolution of the 1980’s paved the way for the rise of the internet and the modern media. The rise of the internet is often traced to the ARPANET, but the world wide web took off beginning 1993 or 1994, and has become ubiquitous ever since. The first handheld mobile phone was demonstrated by John F. Mitchell and Martin Cooper of Motorola in the year 1973, but the mobile revolution did not begin until the mid 1990’s. The smartphone revolution began in 2007 when Apple introduced the iPhone. The use of smartphones has become widespread ever since, and 5G technology has become widespread. Since then social media platforms like Facebook, Whatsapp and Twitter have taken off in a big way. These have led to the amplification and multiplication of horizontal (and lateral) factors, and have changed cultures in a big way, making them adaptive and receptive to new ideas. (Refer our Horizontal–Vertical (and lateral) factors model). Needless to say, this term can be used for language acquisition too, and most individuals today have picked up a smattering of English due to the advent of technology.^{17 18}

The ‘Ethnography of Enculturation’

It is extremely important that a formal and a structured study of the process of enculturation in diverse contexts be carried out. Thus, black box approaches, white box approaches, and brown box approaches to the study of individuals is possible, along with emic and etic approaches too. The “ethnography of enculturation”, as we propose it, would constitute a vital and a crucial link between anthropology, sociology, psychology, and the science of human growth. We must also frown upon and castigate approaches that are impractical, difficult of impossible to implement, but have high-sounding and

¹⁷ Blanchard, Margaret A. (1998). *History of the mass media in the United States: an encyclopedia*. Fitzroy Dearborn. ISBN 978-1-57958-012-4.

¹⁸ Bösch, Frank. *Mass Media and Historical Change: Germany in International Perspective, 1400 to the Present* (Berghahn, 2015). 212 pp

pompous names. On the other hand, the “Ethnography of enculturation” is far from being impractical, and it can indeed be easily and smoothly be accomplished, It can also be combined with long-term ethnography, a concept we had proposed in another paper. It can also be used in identity studies, and to study the process of identity formation in different contexts and scenarios. It can also be used to study how various ideas and beliefs came about. Thus, either a “forward approach” or a “backward approach” can be adopted. In case of the former, an individual is studied either from his childhood or starting from a certain point in his life. In case of the latter, an individual’s thoughts, ideas, and beliefs are traced back to different periods in his life.

Participant observation would be required, often to an elaborate degree, but probably and possibly can never be carried out for years or decades on end. Hence, other techniques such as interviews, questionnaires, surveys, biographical studies, portrait studies and case studies would become necessary. These would complement each other, and a meaningful synthesis of primarily qualitative research techniques should emerge. This approach would also call for human empathy and human touch, (it would also require multi-dimensional contact) and by no means should the subject be intimidated or made to feel uneasy. The author has tried out “Ethnography of enculturation” in various cities in India in the years 2018 and 2019 with a fair degree of success. He had also carried out extensive fieldwork in different cities, and the subjects were from the length and breadth of India. Thus, the “Ethnography of enculturation” would seek to investigate and understand how individuals came to be; it would also seek to investigate their present state in relation to the major and minor factors that shaped them. It would also help ethnographers understand how enculturation takes place in different societies, and how individuals are acculturated in different contexts.

This type of study can be carried out in conjunction with the following techniques (Also note that studies of both individuals and groups can be carried out):

- a. Random approach: Per this approach, a large number of individuals are randomly selected without any pre-conceived biases or notions. This study is totally random, and can be used to draw generalizations.
- b. Statistical Sampling: Statistical sampling is carried out based on meaningful parameters, and these were discussed in our paper which dealt with in some of our earlier papers. This approach would be useful in selecting subjects based on certain attributes.
- c. Outcome-based approach: Per this approach, subjects are selected on the basis of what they have become in life, or their life outcomes. Examples of such individuals could be mavericks, queer personalities, geniuses, goners, downers, feral children, delinquents, alcoholics, successful men and even terrorists and extremists.
- d. Direct approaches: These approaches are based on qualitative and sometimes quantitative techniques examples of which are direct interviewing and participant observation and indirect approaches which are based on secondary sources of information.

e. Forward approaches and historical approaches. In the case of the former kind of an approach, participants are observed from a specific point in time onwards, while in the second case, their antecedents and background is traced through direct or indirect approaches.

f. Cross-sectional study as opposed to longitudinal study: In this type of study, people of different ages are studied on one occasion.

g. Complex pre-planned experiments: This approach would typically involve a great deal of foresight, forethought, and strategizing with a specific goal in sight. Examples of this type of study could include the swapping of toddlers of different ages cross cultures to study the outcome of cultures on the process of identity formation. In some cases, enculturation patterns across generations can be studied, or acculturation patterns of a set of individuals belonging to a specific culture in different contexts and situations.

We had also proposed the idea of long-term ethnography, and in extreme case could have 'Perpetual ethnography' or 'Ethnography in perpetuity' which can be an extremely useful aid in cultural remediation, and will study a culture or a theme perpetually to assess long-term trends and variations. This cannot of course be carried out by a single team, and must necessarily be accompanied by formal handovers. Otherwise, future teams can easily pick up the threads from where the older teams have left off, and this would as such constitute a much more practical and a doable approach. However, there must be a commonality of purpose between different teams too.

Plotting of thoughts ideas and beliefs

We can also state that it is possible to plot ideas, beliefs, thoughts and perceptions based on their centrality to an individual's self, or the core identity of the individual. A scale of one to ten can be conveniently and readily employed in order to achieve a meaningful analysis, and a core idea, belief or thought will naturally have a much lower mathematical value. Wider factors such as the nature or type of movement, educational systems, and legal considerations would play a major role too, and we have been discussing this all along. These ideas and beliefs are also largely shaped by endo, meso and exo environments, and also by the society in general, and in relation to the ideologies that are widespread or prevalent in the society in question. Religion and language are therefore often seen to be central to a person's identity, and thoughts pertaining to religion and language can seldom be painlessly dislodged.

Other thoughts or ideas may however be much more superficial or peripheral, and can be modified easily and relatively much more effortlessly. Thus, some thoughts or ideas often shape identity critically, while many others do not. Usually, thoughts and ideas that leave a permanent (or an indelible) mark on an individual's psyche, impact his identity formation, though this is by no means a rigid rule, or a dogmatic observation. Thoughts that have several lag thoughts attached to them may also shape identity much more centrally than thoughts that do not have lag thoughts attached to them. Thoughts that are received and processed early in an individual's life may also shape his identity more crucially and critically, though this is also again not a hard and a fast rule.

Lead and lag thoughts, ideas or beliefs

Lead thoughts, ideas, beliefs (or perceptions) are those that have other downstream thoughts, beliefs, ideas or perceptions tagged to them in a continuous chain. In such, a change in a lead thought, idea, perception or beliefs can often have far-reaching downstream implications for the individual, and can be the door to better vistas. In such a case, changes can also often be highly disturbing, destructive or shattering. It may therefore also often be associated with what call “eureka points”, “mini eureka points”, moments of epiphany, or Damascus moments, and may be the harbinger of different kinds of change in different contexts and circumstances. Thus, initiation into an ideology or a cult, can lead to a belief in other thoughts and ideals, while enrollment in a new course or degree can bring about positive or meaningful change. A lag thought, idea or belief, on the other hand can usually be changed much more readily, easily and painlessly, with the smallest degree of disruption to an individual’s life or thought patterns, since there are no further downstream thoughts attached to it. It therefore comes without any strings attached. The twin ideas of lead and lag thoughts can also be easily understood by means of a “Chain of thought” analysis.

“Chain of thought” analysis

From the point of view of this paper, “Chain of thought analysis” it is used to study the process of identity formation (and patterns of enculturation) of individuals or a group of individuals in relation to, (or in the context of) a culture or a society; this idea and concept can also be readily and meaningfully used in other avenues in social sciences research, particularly in causal analysis or root cause analysis. This kind of an analysis can be represented diagrammatically either through flowcharts, or through any other alternative approaches such that a pictorial depiction is achieved or accomplished. It can also of course be interfaced with the idea of lead and lag thoughts. Chains of thought can also be aggregated at the level of a group, society or culture in order to discover, formulate, or visualize patterns; this would also be akin to the concept of the widely talked about “patterns of culture” as postulated by Ruth Benedict. This approach can also be therefore readily and productively be used as a part of inductive research techniques, to understand how thought patterns are formulated and birthed in specific contexts.

There are many different real-world examples where a “chain of thought analysis” can be put to productive and beneficial use. For example, we could state that devout or fanatical Muslims believe the Qu’ran is the word of God, so they act completely differently from other individuals, and in accordance with the contents of the Qu’ran. Orthodox Hindus may value the caste system and look down on low caste Hindus. Likewise, some Indians and Americans have an exaggerated sense of nationalistic identity. Marxists also behave in a peculiar and highly irrational fashion, and this may be attributed to their personality. This idea also needs to be understood in the context of group enculturation, group think and all the other concepts proposed by us in this paper and our earlier papers. These also include ideas such as mindspace, thought worlds, world views, mind-orientation, cultural orientation, cultural frame of reference and cross-cultural frame of reference. ^{19 20 21}

¹⁹ Introducing Anthropological Economics: The quest for an Anthropological basis for Economic theory, growth models and policy development for wealth and human welfare maximization Sujay Rao Mandavilli ELK Asia Pacific Journal of Social Sciences Volume 6, Issue 3 (April –June 2020)

Root cause analysis

Root cause analysis (or RCA in short) refers to the process of problem solving which begins by discovering the root causes of common day to day problems and observations (or other technical problems and issues) in order to propose appropriate solutions. According to the philosophy of RCA, it is much more effective to systematically identify root or core causes and propose solutions for them rather than skimming on the surface and snuffing out fires as and when they arise. The philosophy behind RCA therefore states that solving real-world manifestations along on at a time, would not be adequate or sufficient. The root causes are tackled after they are identified, and it is assumed that this method, technique and approach alone would provide lasting solutions to problems. This approach is widely used in fields such as management and technical fields of study such as engineering and information technology too. We strongly recommend that these be used in the social sciences and ethnography too, particularly in identity studies. In case of the latter, causes would usually be human in nature, and either internally induced or externally induced.

Root cause analysis typically comprises the following steps, though variations of the basic theme are indeed possible:²²

- Identification and a clear description of the problem at hand along with the manifest symptoms of the problem.
- Performing the Root cause analysis or RCA and identifying the root cause or causes as the case may be. This may be done manually through the use of various brainstorming, problem solving and creative thinking techniques.
- Distinguishing between the root cause and other causal factors (for e.g., using event correlation techniques or other suitable techniques)
- Providing a clear solution path through evaluation of alternatives, testing, debate, discussion and brainstorming as applicable.
- Execution of the solution which comprises both the corrective action and the preventive action, and testing to see if the problem is solved permanently or not, and whether it might resurface in due course.
- Further study may be carried out if necessary, and an iteration of all the steps may be carried out as well.

Causal analysis or cause and effect analysis

Causal analysis is a type of analysis that is used to identify and address causes of a problem and the various downstream effects and implications of the problem. This technique is widely used to study both

²⁰ Introducing Anthropological Pedagogy as a Core Component of Twenty-first Century Anthropology: The Role of Anthropological Pedagogy in the fulfilment of Anthropological and Sociological objectives Sujay Rao Mandavilli International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology (IJISRT) Volume 3, Issue 7, 2018 (Summary published in Indian Education and Research Journal Volume 4 No 7, 2008)

²¹ Unleashing the potential of the 'Sociology of Science': Capitalizing on the power of science to usher in social, cultural and intellectual revolutions across the world, and lay the foundations of twenty-first century pedagogy Sujay Rao Mandavilli Elk Asia Pacific Journal of Social Science, October – December 2020

²² Landsittel, Douglas; Srivastava, Avantika; Kropf, Kristin (2020). "A Narrative Review of Methods for Causal Inference and Associated Educational Resources". *Quality Management in Health Care*. **29** (4): 260–269

co-relation and causation. Thus, causes and effects are usually identified (and often diagrammatically represented) in a chain. In order to accomplish this, other visual aids such as fishbone analysis are often used. A fishbone diagram is popular and widely used visualization technique that is used to identify the potential causes of a problem, and to represent causes and effects diagrammatically. Other types of modeling techniques are also often used in causal analysis. Often brainstorming techniques, group discussion techniques and individual reasoning and logical analysis are performed to accomplish a cause or effect analysis. This type of analysis has recently found great use in climate change analysis, but from our standpoint, can be readily and fruitfully used in carrying out personality assessments, and enculturation patterns, too. ²³

Causal inference is the process of determining the independent, actual effect of a particular phenomenon that can have various downstream affects. This idea is also related to the concept of inferences of association. Causes and effects may also be represented by means of variables. The science of why things occur is called “etiology”. Concepts in causal inference are widely used in various branches of science, including social sciences. Another useful and popular method of carrying out root cause analysis is to methodically and systematically analyze the changes leading up to an event. Change analysis and event analysis are often used when there are a large number of causes and effects that occur over a lengthy period in time. In order to perform this analysis, every potential cause and effect link is drawn up, and further analyzed. This type of analysis can readily be extended to social science research techniques, and the ethnography of individuals as well and we can call out a “change of events” analysis in this context and connection. ²⁴

Eureka points and Mini-Eureka points

Eureka points and Mini-Eureka points refer to moments of great change in an individual. This word stems for the Ancient Greek term meaning “I have found it”. The Greek polymath Archimedes is said to have uttered this when he was in his bath, though this is sometimes disputed. We had introduced these terms in our two papers on socio-cultural change. The two concepts are essentially the same, though mini-eureka points are essentially a toned down version of eureka points. Other useful concepts are “Damascus moments” and “moments of epiphany” which are also moments of great change in an individual. Life-changing events are however turning points in the life of the individual, and in such a case, the direction of life of an individual also change.

Examples of such turning points could include Gandhi having allegedly been thrown out of a train in South Africa in 1893; the Roman Emperor Caligula’s illness which transformed him into a monster; and Jinnah’s change in stance when he no longer wanted a united India. Shamima Begum who was a part of the infamous Bethnal Green trio is also worth investigating. The life histories of other evil men like Josef Fritzl of Amstetten and Peter Niels the sorcerer can be investigated too. She supported a terror outfit based on her religion in spite of her secular education in the UK. Harilal Gandhi’s life was ruined because his father never sent him to school or charted out a vision for him in life. This approach can also

²³ Rohlfing, Ingo; Schneider, Carsten Q. (2018). "A Unifying Framework for Causal Analysis in Set-Theoretic Multimethod Research" (PDF). *Sociological Methods & Research*.

²⁴ Morgan, Stephen; Winship, Chris (2007). *Counterfactuals and Causal inference*. Cambridge University Press.

be used to investigate the story of geniuses like Michelangelo, Leonardo da Vinci and Avicenna (Ibn Sina), (also the sadly wasted genius of William Sidis, and the disgruntled writer John Kennedy O'Toole) and factors that led to their success. It can also be used to investigate whether geniuses are born or culturally nurtured. It can also be used to assess the life histories of evil men and narcissists like Hitler and Nero. Events can also be studied in relation to the individuals that caused them, examples being the September 11, 2001 World Trade Center attacks, the Oklahoma city bombings of 1995 and the Tulsa race riots of 1921.

In all such cases, some amounts of cognitive dissonance is also resolved, so as to elevate humans to a higher level; we had also discussed different types of cognitive dissonance in our earlier paper, and it would be pointless and futile to reiterate them here. We had also discussed the "Structured apperception techniques for socio-cultural change" in an earlier paper, and in this case, administered "events" could be used to bring about positive and meaningful change by inducing "Eureka points" and "Mini eureka points". We had also discussed the steps that would be involved in the process.²⁵

Interviews

Interviewing can also be used to elicit information about individuals, and obtain a great deal of information about their background. In all such cases, ethics and consent practices must be rigorously followed. Interviewing is a very common technique that is widely used in social science research, but is different from how interviews are understood in day to day parlance, and by the common man. We will now briefly run through some definitions of interviews from a social sciences perspective. In the words of Neuman, "An interview is a short term, secondary social interaction between two individuals with the explicit purpose of one person's obtaining specific information from the other. Information is obtained in a structured conversation in which the interviewer asks pre arranged and pre defined questions and records answers, and the respondent answers to the questions posed to him." (Neuman 1991) Ranjit Kumar in his pioneering book "Research Methodology" states "any structured person to person interaction between two or more individuals with a specific purpose or objective is called an interview." (Kumar 1999) Krishan Kumar defines interview as follows: "interviewing is a process of personal interaction between a researcher and a respondent with a view to eliciting information." (Kumar 1992) In the words of O' Leary, "Interviewing a method of data collection which involves researchers asking respondents questions in order to obtain answers to those questions." (O' Leary 2004)

Interviewing is therefore a face to face interaction with the respondents in order to obtain specific information. The questions are often pre-planned, but the interviewer may also ask more questions as necessary. There are however several intricacies and nuances involved in the interviewing process. This is because human nature is varied and complex, and people may not divulge information easily. Thus, the interviewer must not only be an expert in the subject matter, but must also be an expert in people management; he must understand some human psychology as well.

²⁵ Towards scientific apperception tests for twenty-first century social sciences research: Formulating 'Structured apperception techniques for socio-cultural change' in twenty-first century social sciences research Sujay Rao Mandavilli IJISRT June 2023

There are different types of interviews in use. In some cases, interviewing is done on a one to one basis, while in other cases, there are many interviewees. In a structured interview the interviewer asks the pre-drafted questions with minimal flexibility to change the questions, their sequence, and to add or delete questions. The interview schedule is also pre-fixed, and there is minimal scope to change it. Unstructured interviews are more like free form interviews, and the schedule and the questions are free-form; they can be amply changed during the course of the interview. A semi-structured interview is usually between these two extremes. What type of interview mechanism needs to be adopted would depend on several factors such as the experience level of the interviewer, the possible bias of the interviewer, the topic of study, and the maturity of the respondent. Other aids such as interview guide and interview schedule are also used, and the interviewer must always possess the requisite maturity level and inter-personal skills. The atmosphere during the interview must be free and fair, and the respondent must be prompted only where required. Interviews may also be focused or in-depth and may be fixated on one topic, in other cases, they may be more general. Of late, telephonic interviews and online interviews have also become common.²⁶

Questionnaires

Questionnaires are also used to collect data for the purposes of a downstream analysis. Data in this case is collected usually in a written form. Questionnaires are sent to respondents, who in turn fill in the questionnaire. The questions are usually presented in a structured format and are grouped into convenient heads and categories. The answers provided by respondents become the raw material for further investigative study. Schvaneveldt defined a questionnaire as follows "A questionnaire is a data-gathering device that elicits from a respondent the answers or reactions to a set of printed (or pre-arranged) questions presented and arranged in a specific order." (Schvaneveldt 1985) Krishan Kumar defines a questionnaire as follows, "a questionnaire is a written document listing out a series of questions pertaining to the problem under study, to which the investigator is required to fill out the answers". (Kumar 1992)

The questionnaire must be carefully designed to prompt the right kind of questions. Trick questions and ambiguous questions must be avoided. The questions must also be worded in the appropriate sequence. Either open-ended questions or close-ended questions may be asked. The investigator must therefore not only possess technical knowledge or expertise, but also understand respondent psychology to some degree. In most cases, a covering letter, soliciting the respondent for cooperation and explaining the purpose of the questionnaire is used. The participants must also be assured of the confidentiality of their answers. This assurance will allow the respondents to express their thought freely, and without any fear.²⁷

Focus Group discussions

²⁶ Jamshed, Shazia (September 2014). "Qualitative research method-interviewing and observation". *Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacy*.

²⁷ Foddy, W. H. (1994). *Constructing questions for interviews and questionnaires: Theory and practice in social research* (New ed.). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press

A focus group discussion is a type of qualitative research technique first used in the 1930's. It evolved from a study of group dynamics by Kurt Levin and others. Focus group discussion involves bringing people from similar backgrounds or experiences together to discuss any particular topic. Participants are asked about their attitudes, perceptions, beliefs, opinions and ideas. In a focus group discussion participants are free to talk with other group members and air their views freely; this technique also encourages discussions between participants. It also involves group interviewing in a small group of between eight and twelve people. A moderator is present, and he leads and channelizes the discussion. The atmosphere must be free from fear so that all participants can participate freely. From our perspective, participants of different cultural backgrounds must also be present to add a new dimension to the research. This approach and techniques can also be used to study group enculturation or acculturation processes. This can be used either as a stand-alone research technique, or supplementary to other research techniques.²⁸

Surveys

Surveys are widely used for understanding trends or patterns in a given population or for testing hypotheses. Surveys were used by rulers in ancient times to understand the pulse of their subjects, though surveys in the scientific sense are much more recent. They are also used for identifying characteristics and attributes of a population. They are often used for policy making and policy formulation, though some are carried out purely for academic interest. Sampling is of great importance in a survey. The sample size must not only be adequate, but it must also be representative of the entire population. A common type of survey is an opinion poll which is used to understand the opinions of the public on a specific topic. Surveys regarding religious attitudes and perceptions have been carried out from time to time in the USA, the UK, Iran, Egypt and Turkey. These can be used to ascertain people's points of view, and complement biographical studies. Surveys can be used to aid in enculturation studies by providing a backdrop against which more information is obtained.²⁹

Biographies, case studies and Literature review

A biography is a life-story or a narrative regarding an individual's or a person's life, penned or authored by another individual known as the biographer. A biography may be lengthy and detailed, may be brief, and may contain details regarding the whole of his, or a part of his life. A biography penned by an individual about himself is an autobiography. An auto-biography must be contrasted with an auto-ethnography; in case of the latter, the ethnography is carried out or executed by the individual himself. Biographies are usually very useful in understanding an individual, but a study of biographies must be complemented by other (usually qualitative) research techniques. While relying on a biography, the affiliation of the biographer must also be assessed for bias. Some biographies may be hagiographic in nature, and some others may be critical. Examples of biographies that can be used to illustrate this are biographies of Mahatma Gandhi and Babasaheb Ambedkar by different biographers. In such as case, many biographies may be studied together to achieve a clear picture. The person in question may be living or dead, and may be famous, or not so famous. A case study on the other hand, is a research

²⁸ Morgan, David L. (1996), "Focus Groups". *Annual Review of Sociology*, 22: 129–152

²⁹ Shaughnessy, J.; Zechmeister, E.; Jeanne, Z. (2011). *Research methods in psychology* (9th ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.

method that is employed to gain a better understanding of a particular subject Case studies provide an in-depth insight and research into a given subject, in order to understand all its facets and dimensions thoroughly. Case studies may be classified into critical cases, revelatory cases and unique cases. We have been discussing the concept of a case study off and on in our previous papers.

A literature review forms an important part of a research report. It is used to generate detailed information on the topic being researched and study research carried out on the topic over the years. Research materials and literature reviewed can be from either primary sources or secondary sources, and can come from many sources such as journals, gazettes, books, documents etc. Information can also be collected from magazines and newspapers, though these may be less reliable. Primary literature refers to primary research carried out on a topic. Secondary literature summarizes and synthesizes the primary literature, and may be broader in content than primary literature, though often less intensive. Tertiary literature refers to summaries and condensed versions of research. Sometimes, third party reviews may also be used, though they are often less reliable. The quality of the paper and its authorship must also be borne in mind while carrying out research. Literature review can be used to generate a great deal of information about the individual. Sometimes, audio recordings, video recordings and photographs can also be used. Sometimes historical method can also be used to research dead persons, and we had detailed historical approaches in our papers on twenty-first century historiography.^{30 31}

Use of Inductive approaches and nomothetic rule-building

This approach would also lead to nomothetic outcomes in the long-run and the formulation of generalized rules and context-neutral principles. We have discussed inductive and deductive approaches in a great level of detail in an earlier paper. In case of inductive approaches, a researcher proceeds by studying several individual cases, and then makes generalizations and inferences. On the other hand, in case of a deductive approach (also refer hypothetico-deductive approaches), a statement is made and then tested against more and more data. We had also proposed the concept of Sociological ninety-ten rules. In this case, exceptions of various types are actively sought out. This is critical because exceptions and variations are extremely critical and crucial in social sciences research. Exceptions can also be classified and categorized, and exceptions to those exceptions can be sought out. This would provide a fair degree of reliability and certainty to any exercise, even though social sciences differ from other sciences in that an element of uncertainty always exists. In case of nomothetic approaches, laws are derived from data, while in the case of idiographic approaches, cases are studied entirely on a stand-alone basis.³²

Ethics in ethnography

³⁰ Sidney Lee (1911), *Principles of Biography*, London: Cambridge University Press, Wikidata Q107333538

³¹ Unveiling the Sociological Ninety-ten rules for Social Sciences research: Towards better hypothesis formulation in the Social Sciences in the interests of higher quality research and intellectual multi-polarity Sujay Rao Mandavilli Published in IJSRT, February 2023

³² Making the use of Inductive approaches, Nomothetic theorybuilding and the application of Grounded theory widespread in the social sciences: A guide to better research and theorization in the social sciences Sujay Rao Mandavilli IJSRT May 2023

Ethics refer to the moral principles that govern a person's behavior or interaction patterns with the rest of society. Ethics form the framework to decide what is good and what is bad, and what is acceptable and what is not acceptable in a given situation. They provide criteria and benchmarks for behavior. Ethics are of extreme importance in any form of research dealing with human subjects because the researcher may seek to explore intimate aspects of the participants' lives. The researcher may ensure that ethical boundaries are never transgressed during the course of research, and the subjects are made aware of ethics in research as well, to the extent it is applicable. Such boundaries must also be established as far as possible, before the commencement of the research. Concepts such as that of informed consent and voluntary participation form the bedrock of ethics in ethnographic research. The purpose and scope of the study must of be communicated to the leader of the participants group or all the team members, and consent for their participation obtained. If participants subsequently state that they want the study to be terminated, and all data erased, the researchers must comply with the request. If the ethnographer wants to bring about a change in society, such change must also be acceptable to all members of the group. The idea of ethics in the field of Anthropology stemmed from Franz Boas' observations in 1919.

The American Anthropological Association (AAA) and American Sociological Association (ASA) have both issued detailed and comprehensive statements pertaining to codes of conduct for ethnographic research. The American Anthropological Association has also developed a code of ethics to guide the practice of ethnography. These ethical principles and guidelines were also partly devised in response to earlier ethnographic studies carried out in Northern Thailand among the hill tribes and in Latin America (Project Camelot carried out by the Special Operations Research Office) where ethical considerations were not taken into account during the course of the fieldwork. Thus, the age of value-free research has effectively ended, and ethics must be built into an ethnographic study integrally, and right from the start. Wherever an individual is being researched, his written consent and permission must be obtained. The same would even hold good if an individual is being followed on social media.^{33 34}

We must also bear in mind the following concepts. The dispute of confidentiality: Per this principle, the ethnographer must protect the identities of the subject, and maintain confidentiality wherever asked for. Even if information is given away by the respondent, it must not be used in a manner that will harm their interests. The dispute of consent: Per this principle, the consent of the respondent must be taken wherever the data is being used for downstream purposes. Consent is also required where participant's lives are being probed at any level of detail. The dispute of utility: Per this principle the data obtained from respondents must not be used to put them in a difficult position or harm their interests in any way. The data obtained from respondents must also be useful to them in some way, and must benefit their society. From our perspective, this would be a very important principle, but the subject in question may not always possess the bigger picture and understand how a study might benefit him and his society. The researcher must however be aware of the long-term interests of the participant or respondent, and his society and his culture. He can also then educate him accordingly. The dispute of knowledge and its transmission: Per this concept, the research must be aware of how the research will be used in any downstream exercise, and how the information collected will be used or disseminated in future. The

³³ Barnes, J.A. 1977. *The Ethics of Inquiry in Social Science*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.

³⁴ Bernard, H. Russell 1994. *Research Methods in Anthropology: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. Sage

information and its subsequent use must not harm the interests of the participants in any way, or reach the wrong hands.^{35 36}

Conclusion

We believe that the ‘ethnography of enculturation’ would be a very important part of social sciences research in the twenty-first century. It is also the logical culmination of all our earlier papers including our papers on identity formation and socio-cultural change. It must be executed with a great deal of care and consideration however, and ethics must form the foundation of any such exercise. Such approaches will go a long way in addressing many real-world issues the world faces, as well as the pressing problems of the day. They can also be used in any knowledge-building exercise and building databases and repositories of information in order to reveal patterns of enculturation. This approach can also naturally have any downstream uses and implications such as language planning and the design of education systems, and may other downstream uses and implications may present themselves as the years roll by. This paper could therefore provide us with a research mechanism to better help us understand real-world excesses like the rise of terrorism, and deviant and aberrant behavior. It would therefore not only be an important cog in the wheel in our mission of the “globalization of science”, but would also amplify the utility of social science research techniques in addressing real-world issues and concerns.

³⁵ Beals, R. L. 1969. *Politics of Social Research: An Inquiry into the Ethics and Responsibilities of Social Scientists*. Chicago: Aldine.

³⁶ Weaver, T. 1973. *To See Ourselves: Anthropology and Modern Social Issues*. New York: Scott, Foresman

Annexure

Case studies

We have presented several case studies below, and other researchers may pick up the threads from here, or add more case studies of their own. These individuals can then be researched using the methods we described here, and elsewhere. The author has carried out the ethnography of close to fifty individuals in 2018 and 2019, and these were carried out in different cities in South India in the states of Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh. Respondents were from across the length and breadth of India, including South Indian states and Bihar, West Bengal and Assam, and both Hindus and Muslims were chosen. These case studies may not be of interest to the layman since they are not reknowned or popular figures. The author also does not have permission to reproduce them here. The case studies presented below include both living and dead personalities. Dead persons are mostly included in the interests of confidentiality. We must get permission before we can research living persons.

Case Study Mahatma Gandhi

Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi (2 October 1869 – 30 January 1948) was a famous and a highly influential Indian freedom fighter who employed non-violent methods to lead the campaign for India's independence from British Rule, and later inspired movements for civil rights and freedom in different parts of the world such as the USA and South Africa. He was also known as Mahatma, the great soul, or Bapu, meaning father. He had a rare ability to galvanize masses into action, and unlike Jinnah, was truly a people's leader. He stated on several occasions, that he was a man of the masses, and could never be an intellectual, and this he remained for the rest of his life.

He was born into a reputed Hindu family in Porbander, Gujarat in India, and trained in law in England in the 1880's. Gandhi first used nonviolent civil disobedience in South Africa, where he was practicing as a lawyer. After his return to India in 1915, he began his fight for India's freedom in real earnest. He took up leadership of the Indian National Congress in 1921 and led nationwide campaigns for achieving independence from British rule.

The family's religious background was eclectic and syncretic. Both Gandhi's father Karamchand and his mother Putlibai were staunch and devout Hindus. His mother came from the Krishna bhakti-based Pranami tradition, whose religious texts included the Bhagavad Gita, the Bhagavata Purana, and a collection of fourteen texts with teachings that included the essence of the Vedas, the Quran and the Bible. These helped reinforce his concepts of secularism from a very early age. The Indian classics, especially the stories of Shrivana and King Harishchandra, had a great impact on Gandhi in his childhood. In his autobiography, he admits that they left an indelible impression on his mind. He married in 1883, at the age of fourteen, and left for London in 1888 to study law. After he completed his law in England, a Muslim merchant Dada Abdullah offered Gandhi a job as a lawyer in South Africa. In April 1893, Gandhi aged twenty-three, set sail for South Africa to be the lawyer for Abdullah's cousin. He spent twenty-one years in South Africa, where he developed his political views, outlook on ethics and politics. He faced heavy discrimination in South Africa due to his skin colour. He was often not allowed to walk on footpaths, and was often asked to remove his turban. He was also kicked out of a train for

boarding a first class compartment, and spent the whole night shivering on a railway platform. At a mass protest meeting held in Johannesburg on the 11th of September of 1906 to protest against compulsory registration of Indians, Gandhi adopted his methodology of Satyagraha or devotion to the truth, and nonviolent protest, for the first time. In 1910, Gandhi established, with his friend Hermann Kallenbach, a community called "Tolstoy Farm" near Johannesburg where he developed his policy of peaceful resistance.

Gandhi returned to India in 1915. Gandhi joined the Indian National Congress and was introduced to Indian issues, politics and the Indian freedom struggle by Gopal Krishna Gokhale. Gokhale was a very important leader of the Congress Party known for his restraint and moderation, and Gandhi took Gokhale's approach and modified it to produce a unique flavour. In India, he proved to be a people's person and fought on behalf of farmers in Champaran in 1917, who were forced to grow Indigo by the British. In 1919 after the World War I was over, Gandhi sought political co-operation from Muslims in his fight against British imperialism by supporting the Khilafat movement. This won him Muslim support, but alienated many Hindus. In 1919, he began the Satyagraha civil disobedience, with people assembling to protest the Rowlatt Act. In 1919, British officers opened fire on an assembly of unarmed people, peacefully gathered, participating in a Satyagraha in Amritsar. Gandhi took complete leadership of the Congress in 1920 and began to fight for India's freedom.

Gandhi expanded his nonviolent non-co-operation movement to include the Swadeshi movement – the boycott of foreign-made goods, especially British goods. He asked Indians to wear Khadi instead of British-made textiles. Gandhi exhorted Indians to spin their own Khadi. Gandhi also urged the people to boycott British institutions and law courts, to resign from government employment, and to forsake British titles and honours. Gandhi led the 400 km Dandi Salt March in 1930 to protest the salt tax, and later launched the Quit India movement in 1942. He was imprisoned on many occasions, in both South Africa and India. He lived in an ashram in Sabarmati, Gujarat. He ate simple vegetarian food, and often undertook fasts for self-purification and political protest.

The British government, represented by Lord Irwin, agreed to negotiate with Gandhi. The Gandhi–Irwin Pact was signed in March 1931. The British Government agreed to free all political prisoners, in return for the suspension of the civil disobedience movement. According to the pact, Gandhi was invited to attend the Round Table Conference in London for discussions and as the sole representative of the Indian National Congress. However, British resistance against Indian independence increased in the 1930's, and Gandhi launched fresh Satyagraha in 1936 after a lull.

Gandhi's dream of an independent undivided India was challenged in the early 1940s by Muslim nationalists who were demanding a separate Muslim homeland carved out of India in Muslim majority regions. In August 1947, Britain granted independence, but the British Indian Empire was partitioned into two dominions, a Hindu-majority India and Muslim-majority Pakistan. The partition witnessed massive bloodshed as millions of people migrated to both sides. Hindu Nationalists believed Gandhi was partial towards Muslims, and followed a policy of appeasement. He was therefore assassinated by a Hindu fanatic, Nathuram Godse on 30th January, 1948 due to the pressure he mounted on the Indian government to transfer Rupees 55 crores to Pakistan. Mahatma Gandhi's

idealistic approach, was therefore seen to be at odds with Hindu interests, and Hindu chauvinists seldom understood him.

Gandhi was also influenced by thinkers such as Tolstoy, Ruskin and Thoreau. Gandhi's philosophies evolved with time, and his early ideas became the basis for his later philosophy. His ideas also changed with the cultural context, and some saw him as being disparaging towards blacks in his early years. Gandhi's London lifestyle also reinforced the values he had grown up with. Books that influenced Gandhi most in South Africa were William Salter's "Ethical Religion"; Henry David Thoreau's "On the Duty of Civil Disobedience", and Leo Tolstoy's "The Kingdom of God Is Within You". Ruskin inspired him to live a simple life on the Phoenix Farm in Natal and then on the Tolstoy Farm outside Johannesburg, South Africa. Other theories of influences on Gandhi have also been proposed, including John Ruskin, and Ralph Waldo Emerson. Gandhi was also influenced by the teachings of the Swaminarayan tradition of Hinduism. According to Raymond Williams, he was also influenced by Jainism, particularly by Shrimad Rajchandra, and by Madame Blavatsky. Gandhi had also studied the Bible and the Qu'ran while in South Africa, and was also acquainted with Sufism. All these reinforced his tolerant views which he held throughout his life. However, most of his ideas were based on Hindu philosophy, particularly the Upanishads. He was heavily influenced by the Bhagawad Gita, which he quoted often. His favourable views towards Muslims were based on his study of the Qu'ran. In addition, he read popular books by Charles Dickens, Edward Gibbon, John Ruskin, Jonathan Swift and others which reinforced a cosmopolitan outlook.

Case Study Harilal Mohandas Gandhi

Harilal Mohandas Gandhi (23 August 1888 – 18 June 1948) was the eldest son of Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi and Kasturba Gandhi. He had three younger brothers, Manilal Gandhi, Ramdas Gandhi and Devdas Gandhi. He was the first child of Mahatma Gandhi to survive into his adulthood. He had an elder brother who died in his infancy.

Harilal was born on 23 August 1888, just a few days before his father left for England for higher studies. Harilal remained in India with his mother, but was partially raised by his other relatives. This may have made him bellicose and intransigent in his early years as he lacked the disciplining of his parents, and went wayward under the lenience of his relatives.

Harilal was involved in the Indian independence movement in his early years, and was imprisoned as a satyagrahi six times between 1908 and 1911. His co-operation earned him the nickname of 'Chhota or Little Gandhi'. These were his only golden years in life: he would soon go steadily downhill thereafter and was doomed to fail in life.

He wanted to go to England for higher studies like his father, hoping to become a barrister. His father however firmly opposed this despite having been western-educated himself, believing that a Western-style education would not be helpful in the struggle against British rule over India. This led to tensions between father and son. Harilal had also failed in his matriculation examination, and was seen by his father as not being deserving to be sent abroad. Mahatma Gandhi also put the interests of the nation and society above his own children, and this hurt him. His philosophies were impractical, and he treated his own children just as he would treat any other children. He also failed to provide his son a direction in

life. He was against a material life, but did not chalk out an alternate vision. "You always told me what not to do, but never once did you tell me what to do", his son complained bitterly. Thus, his idea and notions were seen as being at odds with Indian values, and the family system. Eventually rebelling against his father's decision, in 1911 Harilal renounced all family ties, and embarked upon a tragic, lifelong path of self-destruction.

In 1906, he married Gulab Gandhi, with whom he had had five children: two daughters, Rani and Manu; and three sons, Kantilal, Rasiklal and Shantilal. Rasiklal and Shantilal died at an early age. After Gulab died during a 1918 influenza pandemic, Harilal became detached from his own children and his family, and stopped supporting them completely. He became an alcoholic, an embezzler, a debaucher and a vagabond. In June 1935, Mahatma Gandhi wrote a letter to Harilal, accusing him of alcoholism and debauchery. In the letters, Mahatma Gandhi stated that Harilal's problems were more difficult for him to deal with than the struggle for freedom. In May 1936, at the age of 48, Harilal converted to Islam and changed his name to Abdulla Gandhi. However, he converted back to Hinduism and adopted a new name, Hiralal. He stayed in touch with his father sporadically through the years, right up to the death of his father in 1948. Harilal appeared at his father's funeral in such derelict condition that few even recognized him. He himself died on June 18, 1948 due to complications caused by years of heavy drinking. Most of Harilal's problems can be attributed to his lack of a proper upbringing and parental guidance as his father was mostly away, and spent little time on his children. His home schooling which was an experiment in trying to impose moral-based studies over practical knowledge also did not help. This was an attempt in east-west synthesis which mostly failed. He was weak and swayed easily by his friends who lured him to their wicked ways.

His problems therefore stemmed from the lack of an identity, and the absence of a vision for life. This made him weak and very vulnerable. Conflicting values were also to blame: the elder Gandhi wanted to shun a western style education for his son, but instead of attempting to change the system itself, sacrificed his son at the altar of his experiments. "In your laboratory of experiments, my dear father, I am the only truth that has gone wrong. " It was a wrongly concocted mish-mash of incongruent philosophies and ideas that destroyed his life.

Case Study Desmond Tutu

Desmond Mpilo Tutu who was born 7 October 1931 is a South African cleric who was regarded for his work as an anti-apartheid and human rights activist. He was the Bishop of Johannesburg from 1985 to 1986, and then the Archbishop of Cape Town from 1986 to 1996, and the first black African to hold both these positions.

Tutu was born of Xhosa and Motswana descent to a poor family in South Africa. In 1962, he moved to the United Kingdom to study theology at King's College in London. In 1966, he returned to South Africa, and held several teaching positions till 1955. He later held several other positions related to the Christian clergy, and became known for his anti-apartheid work. He also became acquainted with Nelson Mandela, and helped him with his work. He travelled throughout South Africa as a Bishop, and as a Human Rights activist. He was popular with South Africa's black majority, and was regarded for his anti-apartheid struggle, receiving many awards, including the Nobel Peace Prize in 1984. He has also compiled several books of his speeches and sermons, and participated in international and Pan-African

endeavours. He was also influenced by other religions, having completed a dissertation on Islam in West Africa.

Tutu's personality could be traced to his childhood and his upbringing was a product of his Black upbringing and his Catholicism. The 1953 Bantu Education Act, and the separation of races was a turning point in his life. He was also influenced by Bishop Trevor Huddleston, another opponent of apartheid, and some other white bishops as well. The 1976 Soweto rebellion led him to campaign for reform. He declared, "We refuse to be treated as a doormat for the government to tread its jackboots on". His extrovert nature concealed an introvert side and his seriousness and humility; Tutu also had no problem in reconciling his Catholicism with a secular outlook, and his socialist ideology and his desire to live comfortably, and lead an ostentatious life. He was therefore extremely sensitive, and could not tolerate racial slurs.

Case Study Nelson Mandela

Nelson Rolihlahla Mandela (18 July 1918 – 5 December 2013) was a prominent South African anti-apartheid revolutionary and political leader who served as President of South Africa from 1994 to 1999. He was also a Pan-African nationalist and socialist having been influenced by Marxism, and served as President of the African National Congress between 1991 and 1997. He was the country's first black head of state and the first to be elected in a fully representative democratic election. His government focused on dismantling the legacy of apartheid by demolishing institutionalized racism and promoting racial reconciliation and harmony.

Mandela was born to the Thembu royal family in British South Africa, and was of Xhosa heritage. He studied law at the University of Fort Hare and the University of Witwatersrand before taking up employment as a lawyer in Johannesburg. There he became involved in anti-colonial and African nationalist politics, joining the African National Congress in 1943 and co-founding its Youth League in 1944. After the National Party's government established apartheid, a system of racial segregation that discriminated against blacks and coloureds, he swore to overthrow it and establish black majority rule. He was named Nelson by one of his school teachers.

Mandela served twenty-seven years in prison, in both Robben Island, Pollsmoor Prison, and Victor Verster Prison. President F. W. de Klerk released him from prison in 1990, fearing international backlash. Mandela and de Klerk finally ended apartheid, and this resulted in the 1994 multiracial general election in which Mandela's ANC party won, and he became president. Mandela emphasized reconciliation between the country's different racial groups and created the Truth and Reconciliation Commission chaired by Desmond Tutu to investigate past human rights abuses. He also analyzed the causes of inequalities between different racial and ethnic groups. Throughout his life, he was influenced by the philosophies of Mahatma Gandhi, and remained one of his staunchest admirers. He was also proud of his African identity and criticized Western powers.

Mandela received more than two hundred and fifty honours in his lifetime, including the Nobel Peace Prize, and became the subject of a personality cult. He is held in great respect in South Africa, where he is often referred to by his Xhosa clan name, Madiba, and called the "Father of the Nation".

Mandela was more of a practical politician than an intellectual or a theorist. The historian Sabelo J. Ndlovu-Gatsheni described Mandela as a "liberal African nationalist–decolonial humanist", while political analyst Raymond Suttner stated that Mandela displayed a "hybrid socio-political make-up". Mandela took political ideas from other thinkers—among them Indian independence leaders, African-American civil rights activists, and African nationalists—and applied them to the South African context. He however rejected some aspects of their ideals, such as their anti-white sentiment.

Mandela was also a charismatic leader, described by Mary Benson as "a born mass leader who magnetized people". He was image conscious, wore fine quality clothes and cultivated good manners. Mahatma Gandhi was his role model, and he borrowed most of his philosophies from him. He thus preached forgiveness and equality, and avoided vendetta against whites. In addition, Walter Sisulu and Albert Lutuli also influenced him. Walter Sisulu was a South African activist who fought against apartheid, and was a member of the African National Congress. Albert Lutuli was a South African teacher who fought against apartheid, and won the Nobel Prize.

Case Study C. P. Ramanujam

Chakravarthi Padmanabhan Ramanujam (9 January 1938 – 27 October 1974) was an Indian mathematician who worked in the fields of number theory and algebraic geometry. He was born into a Tamil family in Chennai. Like Srinivasa Ramanujan, Ramanujam had a short life. He was elected a fellow of the Indian Academy of Sciences in 1973.

Ramanujam was born to a Tamil family on 9 January 1938 in Chennai, India, the eldest of seven children, to Chakravarthi Srinivasa Padmanabhan. He completed his schooling in Kumbakonam and joined Loyola College in Madras in 1952, and proved to be a prodigy from an early age. He wanted to specialize in mathematics from an early age. His teacher and mentor was Father Charles Racine of Loyola College, who realized that he possessed an originality of thinking and an inquisitive mind.

Ramanujam joined the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research in 1957, and interacted with many mathematicians of repute from around the world. One of his first collaborators was the famous KG Ramanathan.

He began working on a problem relating to the work of the German number theorist Carl Ludwig Siegel, and had simplified the earlier method of Siegel. He took up Waring's problem in algebraic number fields and got interesting results. He also worked on the Kodeira vanishing theorem, and the Milnor number. In recognition of his work, he was promoted to associate professor. He also made great strides in number theory between 1964 and 1968. His work was appreciated by Mathematicians Shafarevich, Alexander Grothendieck and David Mumford with Le Dung Trang. He later worked at the University of Warwick, and was appointed to work at the Indian Institute and Shimla before his death.

He also learnt German, Italian, Russian and French to study mathematical works in their original form. However, he was schizophrenic and prone to depressions. His schizophrenia was first detected in 1964, when he was just 26 years old. He committed suicide at the age of thirty-seven. This can be related to the theory of maverick or queer personality, as he was a genius. He was grounded in a different philosophy and an approach towards life, one of intellectual achievement. Thus, he had difficulty relating to his peers, and his high level of intellectual acumen and intelligence quotient, led him to

overthink. This helped him handle abstract concepts and complexities, assimilate new skills, process new concepts and complex ideas, but now handle his own life. His identity formation was confused because of a mismatch between his own extraordinary ability and the expectations of society. It is widely believed by some psychiatrists that such people are prone to delusional thinking, schizophrenia and dementia. Another case in point was John Forbes Nash who was also schizophrenic. This typically affects individuals between 14 and 40 years of age (sometimes later) and may affect their process of identity formation. However, this may not always be the case among intellectuals, and Einstein and Srinivasan exhibited no such tendencies, even though they were also aloof and weird.

Case Study Albert Einstein

Albert Einstein (14 March 1879 – 18 April 1955) was a German-born physicist who developed the theory of relativity, which is one of the two pillars of modern physics along with quantum mechanics. He was born in Ulm and was schooled in the Luitpold Gymnasium in Germany, and later in Switzerland. He is also known for its influence on the philosophy of science, and the special and general theory of relativity. His equation $E = mc^2$ is often called "the world's most famous equation". He received the 1921 Nobel Prize in Physics for his contributions to theoretical physics.

Einstein's parents were secular, middle-class Jews. His father Hermann Einstein was a featherbed salesman and the owner of an electrochemical factory. Einstein was slow to start talking and did not utter his first words until the age of three. This is now referred to as the "Einstein Syndrome". This even led some teachers to think that he would not be able to accomplish anything in life. Einstein however excelled at maths and physics from a young age, and learnt algebra, calculus and Euclidean geometry in his holidays. He was also attracted towards compasses from an early age, and was fond of playing the violin. Einstein also developed his own proof of the Pythagorean Theorem at the age of twelve. At the age of thirteen, Einstein read Kant's Critique of Pure Reason, and this left a lasting impression on him. He was deeply religious at a young age, though his exposure to science challenged his conservative religious ideas. He graduated in 1900. He held several odd jobs between 1900 and 1902, and married in 1903.

Einstein believed that Newtonian mechanics was not enough to reconcile the laws of classical mechanics with the laws of the electromagnetic field. He therefore, developed a special theory of relativity based on the work of Henri Poincaré and Hendrik Lorentz. In 1905, he published four path breaking papers which made him world-famous at the age of Twenty-six. This included the theory of Brownian motion. He also published a paper on general relativity in 1916 with his theory of gravitation. He later applied the general theory of relativity to model the structure of the universe. He also worked on Unified field theory, and the unification of the basic concepts of physics.

By 1908, he was recognized as a leading scientist and was appointed lecturer at the University of Bern. Einstein was appointed associate professor in the University of Zurich in 1909.

Einstein became a professor at the German Charles-Ferdinand University in April 1911, and published many new scientific works, on topics such as radiation mathematics and quantum theory of solids. In 1912, he returned to Zürich. From 1912 until 1914, he was professor of theoretical physics at the ETH Zurich, where he taught analytical mechanics and thermodynamics. In 1913, he obtained membership to

the Prussian Academy of Sciences in Berlin. In 1916, Einstein was elected president of the German Physical Society, a post which he held till 1918. He joined the academy at the Berlin University in 1914, and became director of Kaiser Wilhelm Institute for Physics in 1917. It was however, his General theory of relativity that made Einstein world-famous in 1919.

In 1920, he became a Foreign Member of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences. In 1922, he was awarded the 1921 Nobel Prize in Physics for his services to Theoretical Physics, and for his discovery of the law of the photoelectric effect. Einstein was elected a Foreign Member of the Royal Society in 1921. He also received the Copley Medal from the Royal Society in 1925.

In 1933, Adolf Hitler came to power in Germany. Because of his Jewish background, Einstein feared persecution and did not return to Germany. He settled in the United States and became an American citizen in 1940. Einstein published more than three hundred scientific papers and more than one hundred and fifty non-scientific works. His intellectual achievements and originality have made the word Einstein synonymous with genius.

In October 1933, Einstein took up a position at the Institute for Advanced Study in the USA. Einstein's affiliation with the Institute for Advanced Study lasted till his death in 1955. During this period, Einstein tried to develop a unified field theory and attempted to refute standard quantum physics, but unsuccessfully. He became an American citizen in 1940. Einstein also joined the National Association for the Advancement of Colored People, and campaigned for the civil rights of African Americans. He also helped establish the Hebrew University of Jerusalem. Einstein was deeply impressed by Mahatma Gandhi. He exchanged letters with Gandhi, and called him "a role model for the generations to come."

Einstein was affiliated with several non-religious humanist groups in the UK and the USA. He served on the advisory board of the First Humanist Society of New York, and was an honorary associate of the Rationalist Association. He died in April 1955, from an internal bleeding caused by a rupture, after having refused surgery.

By his own admission, he was weird on many counts, and his errant behavior led to a divorce with his wife. He smoked excessively, worked odd hours, and even ate insects straight off the ground. He had a disheveled look, never combed his hair, and never wore socks either. Some researchers think his brain was wired differently, contributing to his genius, but there is no consensus on this; upon birth it was noticed that his brain was fifteen percent larger than normal. This included the Parietal lobe, which influenced thinking and memory.

Case Study Muhammad Ali Jinnah

Muhammad Ali Jinnah (25 December 1876 – 11 September 1948) was a lawyer, politician and more widely known as the founder of Pakistan. Jinnah was the leader of the All-India Muslim League from the year 1913 until the birth of Pakistan on 14 August 1947, and then served as Pakistan's first Governor-General until his death in 1948. He is referred to in Pakistan as "Quaid-i-Azam" or Great Leader and "Baba-i-Qaum", or Father of the Nation. His birthday is a national holiday in Pakistan, and he is widely regarded as Pakistan's founder and most important leader.

Jinnah's original name was Mahomedali Jinnahbhai, and was born in 1876, in a wealthy Gujarati family to Jinnahbhai Poonja and his wife Mithibai, in Karachi. Jinnah's family was from a Gujarati Ismaili background, though Jinnah later followed the Twelver Shi'a teachings as a Shi'ite, before ultimately converting to the Sunni sect. Even though his parents were Gujarati, but Jinnah was not fluent in Gujarati, his mother-tongue or even in Urdu. He was more fluent in English, which he usually preferred for most occasions. This also impacted his personality development, as he could not connect with the masses. He was therefore aloof throughout his life, unlike Mahatma Gandhi, who was a man of the masses, and drew large crowds wherever he went. The fact that he was cigar-smoking and pork-eating didn't help either. He may therefore have built upon his attributes, and used them for his benefit for his life, while downplaying his less endearing ones.

He had studied in various English schools and obtained his matriculation from Bombay University. In 1892, a business associate of Jinnahbhai Poonja, offered Jinnah a London apprenticeship with his firm which he accepted. After arriving in London, he gave up the business apprenticeship to study law, joining Lincoln's Inn. Jinnah was influenced by Nineteenth-century British liberalism, and also by Parsi British Indian political leaders like Dadabhai Naoroji and Sir Pherozeshah Mehta. The Western world not only inspired Jinnah in his political life, but also influenced his personal attributes, and his liking for western dress and fashion.

In 1897, Jinnah began his practice in Bombay, as the only Muslim barrister in the city, and had eventually become famous by 1907 as a lawyer, and later as a trade unionist. He also took an interest in national politics, due to which he gave up his practice as a lawyer to plunge full time into politics. Jinnah was affiliated with the Indian National Congress in the first two decades of the 20th century during which time he advocated Hindu-Muslim unity, helping to sign the 1916 Lucknow Pact between the Congress and the All-India Muslim League. Jinnah criticized Gandhi's support for the Khilafat movement of 1920, which he saw as an extremist movement. Jinnah opposed Gandhi's Satyagraha campaign, and believed that self-government should be secured only through constitutional means.

He became an important leader in the All India Home Rule League, and proposed a fourteen-point constitutional reform plan to safeguard the rights of Muslims, before eventually resigning from the Congress in 1920. Thus, in the early days, he advocated a united free India before becoming disillusioned with the concept. Till the 1930's, many Muslims thought they would be part of a unitary state for both Hindus and Muslims as the concept of Pakistan was not even mooted. The early 1930s saw a resurgence in Indian Muslim nationalism, which resulted in the Pakistan Declaration of 1930. In a speech in 1930, Sir Muhammad Iqbal demanded a state for Muslims in Muslim-majority regions of British India. Choudhary Rahmat Ali also advocated a state called Pakistan in North Western India. In subsequent years, Jinnah was to be greatly influenced by Mohammed Iqbal.

The Government of India Act of 1935 delegated power to India's provinces, with a weak central government in New Delhi. Nehru had all along advocated the idea, but the Muslim League initially accepted the proposal. The Congress proved to be more popular in the provincial elections in 1937, and the League did not win even in Muslim majority regions. Jinnah feared Muslims would be marginalized in a united India. In the next two years, Jinnah worked to build support among Muslims for the Muslim League. He restructured the League along the lines of the Congress, appointing a Working Committee,

to run its affairs. By 1939, the Muslim League had million members, and the Muslim League's claims to be the sole representative of Muslim interests received a major boost. Jinnah also rediscovered his own Islamic roots, his own sense of identity, of culture and history, in the final years of his life. Jinnah also increasingly adopted Muslim dress in the late 1930s. Thus, the strength of his own perceived religious identity kept waxing and waning with the passage of time. What is interesting to note that his sense of identity persisted and flourished in spite of having been brought up in a secular and a non-religious environment. It may have been a result of real or imagined prosecution. This is also seen as identity formation by differentiation, and is seen as an important aspect of identity-formation. Thus, polarization leads to fission, and strengthening of the opposition party. By 1940, Jinnah was also convinced that Muslims of the Indian subcontinent should have their own fully independent state. The Muslim League, led by Jinnah, passed the Lahore Resolution, that year, demanding a separate nation for Muslims, and this proposal gradually became popular among many sections of Muslims.

The Congress launched the Quit India movement in 1942. The British government arrested many leaders of the Congress including Gandhi and imprisoned them. In September 1944, Jinnah and Gandhi met, but talks resulted in no substantive agreement. Jinnah insisted on Pakistan being announced prior to the British departure, while Gandhi proposed that plebiscites on partition should occur after independence.

The British people elected the Labour Party and Clement Attlee after the war. The British released a plan for a united Indian state with autonomous provinces, with groups of provinces on the basis of religion. Matters such as defence, external relations and communications would be handled by a central authority. Jinnah and his Working Committee accepted this plan in June, but later rejected it. By December 1946, he insisted on a fully independent Pakistan.

The boundaries of the new state were decided by the Radcliffe commission, and the boundaries of Pakistan included East Pakistan, which later came to be known as Bangladesh. It is believed that fifteen million people relocated between India and Pakistan during and after partition, and it is believed that at least a million may have died. Jinnah did his best for the eight million people who migrated to Pakistan from India, and travelled across the new country and supervised aid and relief measures.

As the first Governor-General of Pakistan, Jinnah oversaw the new nation's government and policies, and initially proposed that the new country be secular. From the 1930s, Jinnah suffered from tuberculosis; only a few people knew about this. He had worked to fight for Pakistan for many years, and totally neglected his health. Jinnah died at his home in Karachi on 11 September 1948 at the age of 71, just over a year after Pakistan's creation.

Some years after his death, historian Stanley Wolpert stated this in a glowing tribute, "Few individuals significantly alter the course of history. Fewer still modify the map of the world. Hardly anyone can be credited with creating a nation-state. Mohammad Ali Jinnah did all three."

Case Study Muhammad Iqbal

Sir Muhammad Iqbal (9 November 1877 – 21 April 1938), also known as Allama Iqbal was a poet, philosopher and politician in British India who inspired Jinnah and the Pakistan Movement. He is also called the "Spiritual Father of Pakistan" for having been among the first to conceptualize Pakistan. He learnt the Qu'ran and Arabic at a very early age. His father was not formally educated, though religious in

orientation. His mother was a humble and a simple woman. He obtained his Bachelor of Arts in philosophy, English literature and Arabic in 1897, and a Master of Arts degree. In 1907, Iqbal went to Germany for his doctoral studies, and earned a Doctor of Philosophy degree from the Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich in 1908. He worked in the Government College, Lahore, before and after his trip to Europe. He also practiced Law till the year 1934.

Iqbal is admired as a poet by Indians, Pakistanis, Bangladeshis, alike, and is called the Poet of the East, and the National Poet of Pakistan. He is also an acclaimed Muslim philosophical thinker of modern times. His first poetry book, "The Secrets of the Self", was published in the Persian language in 1915, and other books of poetry include "The Secrets of Selflessness", "Message from the East" and "Persian Psalms". His best known Urdu works are "The Call of the Marching Bell", "Gabriel's Wing", "The Rod of Moses" and "Gift from Hijaz".

In 1922, he was made a Knight Bachelor by King George V. While studying law and philosophy in England, he became a member of the London branch of the All-India Muslim League. During the Muslim League's 1930 session, he delivered the Allahabad Address in which he advocated the creation of a Muslim state in north-west India, and in the east. When the All-India Muslim League was expanded, Iqbal was made one of the first three joint secretaries of the Punjab Muslim League.

His ideology was different from that of Congress Muslim leaders, and he was also disillusioned with the politicians of the Muslim League. He convinced Jinnah of the need for Pakistan. He thus became the first politician to articulate the Two-nation theory—that Muslims were a distinct nation and deserved political independence from other regions and communities of India.

His love for his religion and religious identity stemmed from his religious upbringing and the values imparted to him by his mother from a very young age. He developed a love for Arabic and Persian as well. This apparently overrode his formal, western education and the fact that he was a converted Indian Muslim with a common 5000 year shared heritage with all other Indians. His ancestors were also Hindu Brahmins, and Saivites, and he referred to this in one of his poems. His strong religious identity also overrode his linguistic and national identity, and goaded him into action. He convinced many Indian Muslims to back his idea of an independent Pakistan, and this ratifies our theory of the 'pecking order of identity'. Thus, Jains, for example did not ask for a separate nation because they shared many cultural traits with Hindus. In their case, national identity was perceived as being stronger than their religious identity.

Case Study Sheikh Mujibur Rahman

Sheikh Mujibur Rahman (17 March 1920 – 15 August 1975) was a Bangladeshi politician and statesman, and the founding father of Bangladesh, and was born in Gopalganj district in Bengal British India in 1920. He was the first President of Bangladesh and later the Prime Minister of Bangladesh from 1971 until his assassination in 1975. He was the driving force behind the independent Bangladesh movement and is referred to as "Bangabandhu" or "Friend of Bengal" by the people of Bangladesh, and also as the father of the nation. He was the leader of the Awami League, an East Pakistan-based political party in Pakistan. Mujib made efforts to gain independence for East Pakistan and was the central figure behind the Bangladesh Liberation Movement and the Bangladesh Liberation War in 1971.

Mujib joined the All India Muslim Students Federation in 1940, as a student of Islamia College. He joined the Bengal Muslim League in 1943 and fought for a united Muslim country of Pakistan. After obtaining his BA degree in 1947, Mujib worked under Suhrawardy during the communal violence that broke out in 1946 in Bengal, just before the partition of India.

After the declaration of Muhammad Ali Jinnah in 1948, selecting Urdu as the national language, protests broke out in East Pakistan, and Mujib became active in the agitation. Sheikh Mujib eventually left the Muslim League and joined the Awami League.

He was elected to the second Constituent Assembly of Pakistan and served from 1955 to 1958. He opposed the renaming of East Bengal as East Pakistan, and worked to increase the power of Bengalis, and eventually strove for an independent Bangladesh.

He opposed the discrimination of Bengalis in Pakistan, who were the majority of the state's population. He proposed a six-point autonomy plan and was jailed during the regime of Field Marshal Ayub Khan for treason and treachery.

Mujib was arrested by the Pakistan Army and sent to prison. This led to major protests and strikes in East Pakistan. The government released Mujib in 1969. He returned to East Pakistan as a public hero. He was given a mass reception and conferred with the title Bangabandhu, or Friend of the Bengal.

Mujib-ur-Rehman managed to garner support throughout East Pakistan, which was home to a majority of Pakistan's population, thus making him one of the most powerful political figures in South Asia. In the Pakistani general elections of 1970, the Awami League under Mujib's leadership won a massive majority. However, he was not invited to form the government.

On 7 March 1971, Mujib called for an independent Bangladesh and asked the people to launch a major campaign of civil disobedience and organized armed resistance at a mass gathering of people held at the Race Course Ground in Dhaka.

The Pakistani army targeted Bengali intellectuals, politicians, union leaders, and ordinary civilians. A major insurgency led by the Mukti Bahini began across East Pakistan. Mujib was arrested, and the Pakistani government refused to release Mujib or negotiate with him. After Indian intervention in December 1971, the Pakistan Army surrendered to the Bengali Mukti Bahini and Indian Army, and a new government was formed.

Sheikh Mujib became the Prime Minister of Bangladesh under a new parliamentary system. He helped to write a new constitution based on nationalism, secularism, democracy, and socialism. The Awami League won a huge mandate in the country's first general election in 1973. However, Mujib faced challenges of unemployment, poverty and corruption, and the Bangladesh famine of 1974. In 1975, he and his family were assassinated by army officers in a coup. This may be seen as a case where linguistic identity overrode religious identity, despite the fact that the latter was particularly strong. This was particularly true when linguistic identity was under strain or being compromised.

Case Study Huseyn Shaheed Suhrawardy

Huseyn Shaheed Suhrawardy (8 September 1892 – 5 December 1963) was a controversial Bengali politician and a lawyer known for his role in the Bengal riots and he was also the fifth Prime Minister of Pakistan between 1956 and 1957.

He was born into a well-to-do Bengali Muslim family in Bengal, and was educated in Calcutta and was trained as a barrister in Oxford where he practiced law at the Gray's Inn in Great Britain. After returning to India in 1921, he practiced as a lawyer, and then joined the Swaraj Party and became the Deputy Mayor of Calcutta under Chittaranjan Das. He was also associated with the Khilafat movement for some time.

Suhrawardy joined the Muslim League, and supported the two-nation theory, and is considered to be one of the founding fathers of Pakistan. Suhrawardy took charge of the only Muslim League-led government after the general elections held in 1945, but was criticized for his alleged role in the Calcutta riots of 1946. Some historians believe that Jinnah allowed Suhrawardy to start a pogrom against Hindus a year before India's independence. He was also criticized for exacerbating the Bengal famine of 1943.

In 1947, Suhrawardy proposed an alternative to the Partition of India, the idea of an independent united Bengal not aligned with either India or Pakistan. This proposed state would include the whole of Assam and north east India. This proposal however, never bore fruit, and parts of Bengal were amalgamated into Pakistan, and came to be known as East Pakistan.

After 1947, Suhrawardy helped integrate East Bengal with Pakistan (this was known as East Pakistan, and later Bangladesh), but split from the Muslim League and established the Awami League in 1949.

After Suhrawardy became Prime Minister, he attempted to address the issue of economic disparities between Western and Eastern Pakistan, as the latter had lagged behind in development and standard of living. His foreign policy resulted in an increased dependency on US foreign aid, and he also supported the Pro-China policy. His government did not last long, and Suhrawardy resigned as Prime Minister after just over a year.

In 1960, he retired from politics, departing for Beirut. He was a chronic heart patient and died in Lebanon in 1963 due to a cardiac arrest. This is a case where an exaggerated sense of religious identity caused an individual to act against his own people, and act in a partisan manner, despite having the highest level of education, and a western-style education.

Case Study Akbar

Abu'l-Fath Jalaluddin Muhammad Akbar (October 1542 – 27 October 1605), or Akbar, was the third Mughal emperor, who ruled from the year 1556 to 1605. Akbar succeeded his father, the weak and ineffectual Humayun to the throne in the year 1556. He was born in Umerkot in 1542. Akbar expanded the Mughal Empire to cover most of the Indian Subcontinent till the Godavari River in present-day Andhra Pradesh. His power and influence, however, extended over the entire subcontinent and many Hindu kingdoms were subservient to him or were his vassals. Akbar established a centralized system of administration throughout his empire, instituted a wide-ranging system of tax reforms, and endeared himself to his Hindu subjects due to his policy of tolerance. His reign marked the zenith of the Mughal Empire.

Akbar's reign greatly altered the course of Indian history. During his rule, the Mughal Empire and greatly increased in power. He created a powerful military and launched wide-ranging political and social reforms. The reign of Akbar was also characterized by commercial growth and foreign trade. By abolishing the Jizya tax on non-Muslims and appointing them to high civil and military posts, he was the first Mughal ruler to win the trust and loyalty of his majority subjects. He encouraged education among both Hindus and Muslims, and encouraged the arts and literature. He founded the syncretic religion of Din-i-ilahi which was doomed to fail, and attracted only a few followers. Akbar was succeeded at the throne by his son, Prince Salim, later known as Jahangir.

Akbar was called "Akbar the Great" due to his many accomplishments. Akbar appointed to his court liberal people including Abul Fazl, Faizi and Birbal.

Akbar allowed Hindus who had been forced to convert to Islam to reconvert to Hinduism without facing the death penalty. He was so regarded by Hindus that his praises were sung in Hindu songs and religious hymns. Akbar also practiced several Hindu customs, and participated in Hindu festivals. He celebrated Diwali, allowed Brahman priests to tie jeweled strings called 'Rakhi' round his wrists in a gesture of goodwill, and invited scholars to participate in debates. He gave up beef and forbade the sale of meats on certain days keeping in mind Hindu sensitivities.

On 3 October 1605, Akbar fell ill with an attack of dysentery from which he never recovered. He died on 27 October 1605, and his body was buried at his mausoleum in Agra.

However, his legacy is negative in Pakistan. Akbar is ignored and rarely mentioned in any school textbook in Pakistan, as opposed to the omnipresence of Emperor Aurangzeb. According to historian Ishtiaq Hussain Qureshi, Akbar had weakened Islam through and it could not be restored to its former status. This interpretation must be ratified through identity theory, and the desire by most people to further their own identity or show it in better light. In India, Hindutva ideologues refuse to consider him tolerant and often slander him. His ideology was shaped by his childhood influences; his father was away for extended periods, and this shaped his individuality, and his thirst for knowledge. He was also influenced by many nobles in the court. He was also influenced by Sufism, and the concept of Sulh-e-kul, or peace to all from an early age. Amongst all the Mughal emperors, he is considered to be the most tolerant, and this endeared him to his Hindu subjects.

Case Study Aurangzeb

Muhi-ud-Din Muhammad (3 November 1618 – 3 March 1707), popularly known as Aurangzeb (Ornament of the Throne) or Alamgir (Conqueror of the World), was the sixth Mughal emperor, who ruled over almost the entire Indian subcontinent for close to half a century. He was the last major monarch of the Mughal Empire, though his policies sowed the seeds of the disintegration of the Mughal Empire. The Mughal Empire greatly declined after his death in 1707, and disappeared in 1857.

Aurangzeb was an accomplished military leader and conqueror; during his reign, the Mughal Empire reached its greatest extent, covering even most of South India. The extent of the Mughal Empire increased to 4 million square kilometres, and he ruled over a population of over 158 million subjects, with an annual revenue of \$450 million in 1690. Aurangzeb was pious and was a religious

zealot; he memorized the entire Quran, studied the hadiths and observed the festivals of Islam, antagonizing his Hindu subjects in the process. He did not enjoy a luxurious life and his personal expenses and constructions of small mosques were covered by his own earnings, such as the sewing of caps and sales of his handwritten copies of the Quran.

Aurangzeb abandoned his predecessors' legacy of pluralism and religious tolerance, introducing the jizya tax, destroying Hindu temples, executing his elder brother Dara Shukoh, Maratha king Sambhaji and the ninth Sikh guru Tegh Bahadur, and the prohibition of activities forbidden in Islam including gambling, drinking, music, and premarital sex.

Aurangzeb was born on 3 November 1618, in Dahod, Gujarat. He was the third son and sixth child of Shah Jahan and Mumtaz Mahal. In 1626, Aurangzeb and his brother Dara Shukoh were kept as hostages under their grandparents' Jahangir and Noor Jahan Lahore court. On 26 February 1628, Shah Jahan became the Mughal Emperor, and Aurangzeb returned to live with his parents at Agra Fort, where Aurangzeb received a formal education in Arabic and Persian.

In his early days, Aurangzeb was in charge of the army sent to Bundelkhand to defeat the ruler of Orchha, Jhujhar Singh. The campaign was successful and Singh was removed from power. Aurangzeb was appointed viceroy of the Deccan in 1636. Shah Jahan dispatched Aurangzeb, who in 1636 brought the Nizam Shahi dynasty to an end. In 1637, Aurangzeb married princess Dilras Banu Begum. She was his first wife and chief consort and his favourite. In 1644, Aurangzeb's sister, Jahanara, suffered burns in an accident. Aurangzeb incurred his father's displeasure by not returning to Agra immediately but three weeks later. Shah Jahan was outraged to see Aurangzeb enter the palace late, and in military attire and dismissed him from his position of viceroy of the Deccan; In 1645, he was barred from the court for seven months. Thereafter, Shah Jahan appointed him governor of Gujarat where he did well and was praised for restoring stability and peace.

In 1647, Shah Jahan moved Aurangzeb from Gujarat to be governor of Balkh, in lieu of Murad Baksh, who had proved ineffective there. By the end of this two-year campaign, a vast sum of money had been expended for little gain.

Aurangzeb was later appointed governor of Multan and Sindh. His efforts to defeat the Safavids at Kandahar, ended in failure. Aurangzeb became viceroy of the Deccan again and helped the Deccan return to prosperity.

The four sons of Shah Jahan all held governorships during their father's reign. The emperor favoured the eldest, Dara Shukoh as his successor. This had caused resentment among the younger three, who sought at various times to strengthen alliances between themselves and against Dara. Dara was an intellectual and a religious liberal like Akbar, while Aurangzeb was much a more conservative Muslim. Dara was also a poor general and leader. The loyalties of officials were motivated more by their own interests, the closeness of the family relation and the charisma of the sycophants than by ideological divides. Jahanara, was well-regarded by Aurangzeb even though she shared the religious outlook of Dara.

Having declared that he wanted Dara to succeed him, Shah Jahan took ill in 1657 and was under the care of his favourite son in Shahjahanabad in Old Delhi. Rumours of the death of Shah Jahan circulated and the younger sons were concerned that Dara might be hiding it for his own selfish motives. Thus, they

took action: Shah Shuja In Bengal, where he had been governor since 1637, Prince Muhammad Shuja crowned himself King at RajMahal, while Murad did the same in his governorship of Gujarat and Aurangzeb did so in the Deccan.

After regaining some of his health, Shah Jahan moved to Agra and Dara urged him to send forces to challenge Shah Shuja and Murad, who had declared themselves rulers in their respective territories. While Shah Shuja was defeated at Banares in February 1658, the army sent to deal with Murad discovered to their surprise that he and Aurangzeb had combined their forces. In the battle that followed, Aurangzeb became the victor. Neither Dara's men nor his generalship were any match for Aurangzeb. After the defeat of Dara, Shah Jahan was imprisoned in the fort of Agra where he spent eight years under the care of his daughter Jahanara.

Murad was executed on 4 December 1661, and Shuja was also killed. With Shuja and Murad disposed of, Aurangzeb killed Dara Shikoh as well. In 1658, Aurangzeb was coronated in Delhi.

Aurangzeb was an orthodox Muslim ruler. Reversing the tolerance of his predecessors, he tried to make Islam a dominant force in his reign. These efforts brought him into conflict with the Hindus.

In spite of his intolerance, Aurangzeb's bureaucracy employed more Hindus than that of his predecessors. Between 1679 and 1707, the number of Hindu officials in the Mughal administration rose by half, many of them Marathas and Rajputs. Under Aurangzeb's reign, Hindus rose to represent 31.6% of Mughal nobility, the highest in the Mughal era.

He imposed Jizya, a military tax on non-Muslims in the year 1679. Further, Aurangzeb levied discriminatory taxes on Hindu merchants at the rate of 5% as against 2.5% on Muslim merchants.

During his reign, Aurangzeb ordered the destruction of many temples and some mosques. He ordered the destruction of Vishvanath Temple at Varanasi for being a centre of conspiracy against the state, and the Jama Masjid at Golkunda after finding out that its ruler had built the mosque in order to hide revenues from the state.

Aurangzeb displayed a particular hatred towards Hindus and their temples. As a result of his fanaticism, thousands of the temples which had represented or housed the art of India through a millennium were laid in ruins. However, other historians he claimed he built temples.

In 1689, the Maratha King Sambhaji was executed by Aurangzeb as he was found guilty of murder and violence, atrocities against Muslims. In 1675 the Sikh leader Guru Tegh Bahadur was arrested by Aurangzeb, found guilty of blasphemy and executed. The leader of the Dawoodi Bohra sect, Syedna Qutubkhan Qutubuddin was also executed by Aurangzeb for heresy.

Aurangzeb's ideals stemmed from his austere upbringing and dedication to Islam. This case study however shows that there are wide variations among individuals, and that individual preferences can override enculturation. For, example, did not adopt the tolerant attitude of his brother Dara, and jettisoned the tolerant attitude of his predecessors. Individual experiences, and the desire to act differently can make a huge difference here.

Case Study Asaduddin Owaisi

Asaduddin Owaisi (born 13 May 1969) is an Indian politician, and the President of the Hyderabad-based All India Majlis-e-Ittehadul Muslimeen. He is also a Member of Parliament, representing the Hyderabad constituency in Lok Sabha.

Owaisi was born to Sultan Salahuddin Owaisi and Najmunnisa Begum. He comes from a leading political family, and his grandfather Abdul Wahed Owaisi launched the All India Majlis-e-Ittehadul Muslimeen in 1957. Owaisi belongs to the Hyderabad-based All-India Majlis-e-Ittehadul Muslimeen (AIMIM) party. He completed his graduation in Bachelor of Arts from Nizam College in Hyderabad. His brother Akbaruddin Owaisi is a Member of Telangana Legislative Assembly and heads the party in the state. His youngest brother Burhanuddin Owaisi is the editor of Etemaad. The party, while opposed to extremism and terrorism, still practises a politics of "competitive chauvinism," to attract Muslim votes.

Several analysts compare Owaisi to Jinnah. According to Patrick French, Owaisi appeals to non-sectarian Muslim identity, and is more moderate than his brother. His brand of Islamism with nationalism are popular in both Hyderabad and Mumbai, where Muslim youth get radicalized easily.

Owaisi states that his fight is within the framework of the Indian constitution. He says that the secular parties of India have not been able to appeal to Muslims. While the parties claim not to discriminate against Muslims, they in practice divide the electorate, and marginalize Muslims. Hence, Muslims must develop their own political force, like other OBCs, and Dalits.

His views are seen to be moderate, and in odds with his own brother's more radical views on Islam. This implies that there is a strong personal element in the process of enculturation, and there can be wide variations between individuals.

Case Study Akbaruddin Owaisi

Akbaruddin Owaisi (born 14 June 1970) is an Indian politician and an MLA of the Telangana Legislative Assembly. He is a member of All India Majlis-e-Ittehadul Muslimeen and is its floor leader in the Telangana Legislative Assembly.

Owaisi was born in Hyderabad on 14 June 1970. His mother is Nazima Begum. Owaisi is married to Sabina, with and has a daughter and a son.

Owaisi has been elected as the Member of the Legislative Assembly for Chandrayangutta constituency several times. He served as a deputy to his elder brother Asaduddin Owaisi, who then led the MIM in the House.

In August 2007, Owaisi made death threats against Tasleema Nasreen, stating that the fatwa against her and Salman Rushdie would be carried out. In April 2012, Owaisi made derogatory and demeaning comments against Hindu God Rama and his mother Kaushalya. Owaisi asked "Where all did Ram's mother go wandering and where did she give birth to him".

On 12 December 2012, Owaisi made derogatory remarks with hand gestures about Hindu goddess at a public rally in Nizamabad. He said making hand gestures – "She, who is sitting," and added, "What is this new name Bhagyalakshmi, never heard of her. Shout such slogans such that the Bhagya also shakes and Lakshmi also falls down."

On 22 December 2012, Owaisi addressed a rally in Adilabad district of Andhra Pradesh. In his speech, Owaisi made comments against Hindus, Hindu deities, Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh, Vishva Hindu Parishad, Bharatiya Janata Party. He referred to the Hindus as "impotent" and the Indian police as the "impotent army". Owaisi justified the Mumbai bombings of 1993 by saying they were a reaction to the demolition of Babri Masjid and atrocities on Muslims in India. Owaisi mocked Hindu cremation by saying "when you (Hindus) die, you become air after burning and go astray." Owaisi talked in derogatory terms about heritage places of India including Ayodhya, Ajanta Caves and Ellora Caves. He said that if Muslims go away from India, they will take the Taj Mahal, Red Fort and Qutb Minar with them, adding "What will then remain here? Just a razed Ram temple in Ayodhya and naked statues of Ajanta." He made highly inflammatory speeches and on one occasion said, "Remove police for 15 minutes, we will finish off 1 billion Hindus."

Many people and organizations criticized Owaisi for his speeches. The Andhra Pradesh Bharatiya Janata Party president, G. Kishan Reddy called for booking Owaisi, stating that "...religious bigotry, incitement of religious sentiments and contemptuous insinuation against Hindu gods and goddesses formed the crux of the speeches of a person who was sworn in as an MLA". In a statement issued by the Confederation of Voluntary Associations (COVA), several social activists criticized the speech saying that such speeches will lead to division of society, violation of peace and conflicts. These included Asghar Ali Engineer, Swami Agnivesh, Mahesh Bhatt, Hamid Mohammed Khan, Sandeep Pandey, Ram Puniyani, and others.

It is interesting to note that his own brother Asasuddin Owaisi is seen as a moderate leader. Thus, there can be wide variations between individuals.

Case Study A. P. J. Abdul Kalam

Avul Pakir Jainulabdeen Abdul Kalam (15 October 1931 – 27 July 2015) was an aerospace scientist who was the 11th President of India between 2002 and 2007. Avul Pakir Jainulabdeen Abdul Kalam was born on 15 October 1931 to a Tamil Muslim family in Rameswaram, then in the Madras Presidency and now in the State of Tamil Nadu. His father Jainulabdeen was a boat owner and imam of a local mosque; his mother Ashiamma was a housewife. His father was the owner a ferry that took Hindu pilgrims between Rameswaram and Dhanushkodi. Kalam was the youngest of four brothers and one sister in his family.

After graduating from the Madras Institute of Technology in 1960, Kalam joined the Aeronautical Development Establishment of the Defence Research and Development Organization as a scientist and became a member of the Defence Research & Development Service. He could not achieve his dream of becoming a fighter pilot, as he did not qualify. In 1969, Kalam was transferred to the Indian Space Research Organization where he was the project director of India's first Satellite Launch Vehicle (SLV-III) which deployed the Rohini satellite in 1980. He was known as the Missile Man of India for his work on the development of missiles and rockets.

Religion and spirituality were very important to Kalam throughout his life. In fact, he made his own spiritual journey the subject of his final book, *Transcendence: My Spiritual Experiences with Pramukh Swamiji*.

A proud and practicing Muslim, namaz and fasting during Ramadan were integral to Kalam's life. His father, the imam of a mosque in his hometown of Rameswaram, had instilled these Islamic values in him. His father also taught the young Kalam the value of interfaith respect and dialogue. As Kalam stated: "Every evening, my father A.P. Jainulabdeen, an imam, Pakshi Lakshmana Sastry, the head priest of the Ramanathaswamy Hindu temple, and a church priest used to sit with hot tea and discuss the issues concerning the island." Such early exposure convinced Kalam that the answers to India's multitudinous issues lay in "dialogue and cooperation" among the country's religious, social, and political leaders. Moreover, since Kalam believed that "respect for other faiths" was one of the key teachings of Islam. As Kalam stated, "For great men, religion is a way of making friends; small people make religion a fighting tool."

Kalam was elected as the 11th President of India in 2002 with the support of both the ruling Bharatiya Janata Party and the then-opposition Indian National Congress. Widely referred to as the "People's President", he returned to education, writing and public service after a single term. He was the recipient of several prestigious awards, including the Bharat Ratna, India's highest civilian honour.

While delivering a lecture at the Indian Institute of Management Shillong, Kalam collapsed and died from a cardiac arrest on 27 July 2015, at the age of 83. Thousands of dignitaries attended the funeral ceremony held in Rameshwaram, where he was buried with full state honours.

One reason for Kalam's widespread popularity among diverse groups in India was his respect for the many spiritual and cultural traditions of India. In addition to his faith in the Koran and Islamic practice, Kalam was well-versed in Hindu traditions; he learnt Sanskrit, read the Bhagavad Gita and he was a vegetarian.

Case Study Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant

The Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL), also known as the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS), or Daesh is a Salafi jihadist militant group and former defunct self-styled state that followed a fundamentalist, Salafi version of Sunni Islam. ISIL rose to notoreity in 2014 when it drove Iraqi government forces out of key cities, followed by its capture of Mosul and other cities.

The group is regarded as a terrorist organization by the United Nations and many countries, and may be the most extremist organization in history. ISIL is widely known for circulating videos of beheadings and executions of soldiers and civilians, including journalists and aid workers, and the destruction of cultural heritage sites such as the ancient Roman site of Palmyra. The United Nations holds ISIL responsible for several human rights abuses and war crimes. ISIL also committed ethnic cleansing on a historic and unprecedented scale in northern Iraq.

ISIL originated as Jama'at al-Tawhid wal-Jihad in 1999, and followed al-Qaeda's footsteps. ISIL is a Salafi or Wahhabi group. ISIL's ideology is based on a radical interpretation of Salafi Islam, a strict, puritanical form of Sunni Islam. It claims religious, political and military authority over all Muslims worldwide. ISIL promotes religious violence, and regards Muslims who do not agree with its interpretations as infidels or apostates. ISIL aims to return to the early days of Islam, rejecting any innovations in the religion which it labels Bidah.

In Syria, the group conducted ground attacks on both government forces and opposition factions and by December 2015, it held a large area extending from western Iraq to eastern Syria, containing an estimated 8 to 12 million people, where it enforced its writ strictly. ISIL was once operational in 18 countries across the world, including Afghanistan and Pakistan. In July 2017, the group lost control of its largest city, Mosul, to the Iraqi army and continued to lose territory to the various states and other military forces allied against it. By 2019, the group had effectively been vanquished.

ISIL was headed by Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi, the Islamic State's self-styled Caliph who was believed to have been killed in 2019.

Its actions have been widely criticized, with the United Nations, various governments and mainstream Muslim groups rejecting its ideals. Around the world, Islamic religious leaders have condemned ISIL's ideology and actions, arguing that the group has strayed from the path of Islam and that its actions do not reflect the religion's teachings or virtues. According to a poll by Pew Research Center, Muslim populations of various countries have strongly negative views of ISIL. However, many Muslims are enamored of it, and have dreamt of joining it. There have even been Indian recruits to ISIL. This is related to the process of enculturation, and many are even educated ones, holding Ph.D's. This quashes the notion that education alone is enough to fight terrorism. The nature of education might count, too. One aspect to be borne in mind is that the founding fathers of the group were taught theology, and not imparted a secular education.

Case Study Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi

Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi was the leader of the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL) militant terrorist organization. ISIL has been designated a terrorist organization by the United Nations, European Union and many individual states, while al-Baghdadi is considered a Specially Designated Global Terrorist by the United States. Since 2016, the U.S. State Department has offered a reward of up to \$25 million for information or intelligence leading to his capture or death.

Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi has had other names, including Abu Du'a , Al-Shabah, and Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi al-Husseini al-Hashimi al-Qurashi). He is known to his supporters as Amir al-Mu'minin, (Caliph), Caliph Abu Bakr, Caliph al-Baghdadi, or Caliph. This is besides his previous epithet, which was Sheikh Baghdadi,

Al-Baghdadi was born near Samarra, Iraq, in 1971 as the third of four sons. He was born as a member of the tribal group called the Al-Bu Badri tribe. Al-Baghdadi also claimed that he was descended from the Quraysh tribe and therefore from Muhammad. His father, Sheikh Awwad, was highly religious. Awwad taught the teenaged Baghdadi, to lead children in a neighbourhood to chant the Quran. His mother was a very religious person. His friends described him in his youth as being shy, unimpressive, a religious scholar, and a man who eschewed violence.

As high-school grades were not good enough for him to study law, educational science and languages at the University of Baghdad, he attended the Islamic University of Baghdad, where he studied Islamic law and the Quran and obtained a BA, MA, and PhD in Islamic studies from the University. He became an Islamic revolutionary in 1991, and was arrested by the US forces in 2004.

Al-Baghdadi remained leader of the ISI until its formal expansion into Syria in 2013 when he announced the formation of the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL) – or the Islamic State in Iraq and Syria (ISIS).

On 29 June 2014, ISIL announced the establishment of a worldwide caliphate. Al-Baghdadi was named its caliph, and the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant was renamed the Islamic State (IS). Abu Bakr Al-Baghdadi is designated by the United States Department of State as a Specially Designated Global Terrorist. The U.S. Department of State's Rewards for Justice Program identifies Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi as a senior leader of the terrorist organization Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL), and as being "responsible for the deaths of thousands of civilians in the Middle East, including the brutal murder of numerous civilian hostages from Japan, the United Kingdom, and the United States". He was a highly educated man. This quashes the notion that education alone is enough to fight terrorism. The nature of education might count, too. One aspect to be borne in mind is that he was taught theology, and not imparted a secular education.

Case Study Shamima Begum

This article is about Shamima Begum who travelled to Syria with two friends in February 2015. Shamima Begum (born c. 2000) is a British-born woman who left the UK in February 2015, aged 15, to join the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL) in Syria. Her intention to return to the UK in February 2019 resulted in a public debate about the handling of returning jihadists.

Begum was born in England to parents of Bangladeshi heritage. She lived in Bethnal Green where she attended the Bethnal Green Academy. Together with her friends Amira Abase and Kadiza Sultana, she left the UK in February 2015, at the age of fifteen. They joined the ISIS in Syria.

After arriving in Syria, she married Dutch-born Yago Riedijk, who had converted to Islam and arrived in Syria in October 2014. She had three children. The elder two died. Her youngest child was born in a refugee camp in February 2019 and, in March 2019, also died.

Begum served in ISIL's "morality police", carried a Kalashnikov rifle and was a strict enforcer of ISIL's laws, such as dress codes for women.

On 13 February 2019, The Times' war correspondent Anthony Loyd found Begum at the Al-Hawl refugee camp in Northern Syria. When interviewed, Begum revealed that she was nine-months pregnant and hoped to return to the UK to raise her child, but did not regret her decision to join ISIL. She also claimed she supported some British values. It was noted that she continued to support the ISIL ideology and justify its barbarism. The British government stripped her of her citizenship, leaving her stateless.

On 3 May, Bangladeshi foreign minister Abdul Momen stated that if she entered Bangladesh she would face the death penalty due to the nation's "zero tolerance policy" towards terrorism. She was radicalized even though she was brought up in the UK. Her father was also secular.

Case Study Osama bin Laden

Osama bin Mohammed bin Awad bin Laden (March 10, 1957 – May 2, 2011), or Osama bin Ladin, was a terrorist who was the founder of the Islamic militant organization al-Qaeda. He was a Saudi Arabian citizen until 1994 (stateless thereafter), and a member of the bin Laden family.

Bin Laden's father was Mohammed bin Awad bin Laden, a Saudi millionaire from Hadhramaut, Yemen and the founder of the construction company, Saudi Binladin Group. His mother, Alia Ghanem, was from a middle-class family in Syria. He was born in Saudi Arabia and studied until 1979, when he joined Mujahideen forces in Pakistan fighting against the Soviet Union in Afghanistan. He helped to fund the Mujahideen by diverting arms, money and fighters from Arab countries into Afghanistan. In 1988, he formed the al-Qaeda. He was banished from Saudi Arabia in 1992, and moved to Sudan, until U.S. pressure forced him to leave Sudan in 1996. After establishing a new base in Afghanistan, he declared a war against the United States, initiating a series of terrorist attacks. Bin Laden is well known for his role in the September 11 attacks, which resulted in the deaths of nearly 3,000 people and prompted the United States to take retaliatory action. He therefore became the subject of a decade-long international manhunt. On May 2, 2011, bin Laden was shot and killed by United States Navy in Pakistan.

The al-Qaeda leader believed that U.S. foreign policy has oppressed, killed, or harmed Muslims worldwide. Bin Laden also criticized the U.S. for its secular form of governance, calling upon Americans to convert to Islam and "reject the immoral acts of fornication, homosexuality, intoxicants, gambling, and usury".

His viewpoints and methods of achieving them had led to him being designated as a terrorist by scholars, journalists from The New York Times, the BBC, and Qatari news station Al Jazeera, and other analysts. Bin Laden was also heavily anti-Semitic, stating that most of the negative events that occurred in the world were the direct result of Jewish actions. He was a radical Islamist in spite of having been exposed to Western values since an early age.

Case Study K. B. Hedgewar

Keshav Baliram Hedgewar (1 April 1889 – 21 June 1940), was the founder of the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS). Hedgewar founded the RSS in Nagpur in 1925, with the intention of promoting the concept of a united India rooted in Hindutva ideology.

Hedgewar was born in 1889 in a Marathi Brahmin family in Nagpur. His parents were Baliram Pant Hedgewar and Revati. They were originally from a village called Kandurti in Andhra Pradesh, and Hedgewar's forefathers had moved to Nagpur a few generations back. When Keshav was thirteen, both his parents died of plague. His elder brothers, Mahadev and Sitaram Pant ensured that he received a good education.

When he was studying in Neel City High School in Nagpur, he was expelled from the school for singing "Vande Mataram" in violation of the circular issued by the British government. As a result, he had to pursue his high school studies at the Rashtriya Vidyalaya in Yavatmal and in Pune. After matriculating, he went to Kolkata to pursue his medical studies. After passing the L.M.S. Examination in 1914, he returned to Nagpur in 1915 to practice as a physician.

Hedgewar actively participated in Indian National Congress in the 1920s, but wanted an alternate model of nation-building in India. He was influenced by Lokmanya Bal Gangadhar Tilak and Vinayak Damodar Savarkar. He considered that the cultural and religious heritage of Hindus should be the basis of Indian nationhood.

Hedgewar founded RSS in 1925 on the day of Vijayadashami with an aim to organize Hindu community for its cultural and spiritual regeneration and make it a tool in getting the country free from foreign domination. The Sangh (Organization) was growing in Nagpur and the surrounding districts, and it soon began to spread to other provinces.

After founding the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh in 1925, Hedgewar started the tradition of keeping the RSS away from the anti-British Indian Independence movement. The RSS carefully avoided any political activity that could be construed as being anti-British. Mahatma Gandhi gave a call for 'Satyagraha' against the British Government. Gandhi launched the Salt Satyagraha undertaking his Dandi Yatra. Dr. Hedgewar participated only individually and not let the RSS join the freedom movement officially. Hedgewar's lack of enthusiasm in Independence Movement is oftencriticized by Anti-RSS groups. According to some, Hedgewar actively discouraged RSS cadres to not join the independence movement which was led by Gandhi.

His health deteriorated in later years of his life. He started delegating his responsibilities to M. S. Golwalkar, who later succeeded him as Sarsanghachalak of RSS. Hedgewar was described as "a great son of Mother India" by former President of India Pranab Mukherjee during his visit to Hedgewar's birthplace in Nagpur.

Case Study M. S. Golwalkar

Madhav Sadashiv Golwalkar (19 February 1906 – 5 June 1973) was the second Sarsanghchalak of the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh. Golwalkar authored the books "Bunch of Thoughts" and "We, or Our Nationhood Defined".

Golwalkar was born on 19 February 1906 to Sadashivrao and Lakshmibai in a well-to-do Marathi Brahmin family near Nagpur in Maharashtra. Sadashivrao, a former clerk in the Posts and Telegraphs Department, became the headmaster of a high school. Golwalkar was a good student. In 1922, Golwalkar enrolled in Hislop College, a missionary-run educational institute in Nagpur. At the college, he was angry at the disparagement of Hinduism. In 1924, Golwalkar left Hislop College for Benaras Hindu University (BHU) in Varanasi, receiving a Bachelor of Science degree in 1925 and a master's degree in biology in 1927. He was influenced by Madan Mohan Malaviya, a nationalist leader and founder of the university. He later taught zoology for three years at BHU. Golwalkar returned to Nagpur, and obtained a law degree by 1935. In 1931, Hedgewar visited Benares and was attracted to the ascetic Golwalkar. Hedgewar encouraged him to pursue a law degree because it would give him the reputation required of an RSS leader. In 1934, Hedgewar made him secretary of the main Nagpur branch. After he began practicing law, Hedgewar tasked him with the management of the Akola Officers' Training Camp. In October 1936, Golwalkar abandoned his law practice and RSS work for the Sargachi Ramakrishna Mission ashram in West Bengal to become a sanyasi.

Hedgewar began grooming him for leadership and he was placed in charge of the All-India Officers' Training Camp from 1937 to 1939. His book, "We, or Our Nationhood Defined", came to be regarded as a treatise of RSS ideology.

RSS supreme leader for more than 30 years, Golwalkar made it one of strongest religious-political organizations in India; its membership expanded from 100,000 to over one million, and it branched out

into the political, social, religious, educational and labour fields through 50 front organizations. The RSS extended to foreign countries, where Hindus were recruited into organizations such as the Bharatiya Swayamsevak Sangh or the Hindu Swayamsevak Sangh. There was an important shift in the RSS worldview. One of Golwalkar's major innovations was an anti-communist, anti-socialist ideology which made it popular with the wealthy sections of Indian society.

Under his leadership, the RSS still remained aloof from the freedom movement, and connections with the Hindu Mahasabha were severed.

When Mahatma Gandhi was assassinated in January 1948 by Nathuram Godse, there was apprehension that the RSS was involved. Golwalkar and 20,000 swayamsevaks were arrested on the 4th of February of that year, and the RSS was banned for promoting violence and hatred. Golwalkar tried to negotiate with Home Minister Vallabhbhai Patel about having the ban lifted. The mass arrests, violence against members and the ban by an independent Indian government of what it considered to be a patriotic organization was a shock to the RSS membership.

Golwalkar propagated an anti-Muslim view in his books. In his "Bunch of Thoughts", Golwalkar branded Muslims, Christians and Communists as India's 'internal enemies'. A book based on extracts of his writings, titled "Guruji: Vision and Mission", included a chapter titled "Hindu—the Son of this Motherland," which claimed that the term 'Bhartiya' did not include Muslims, Christians or Parsis, and that only Hindus could truly represent the term. However, Jains, Buddhists and Sikhs were considered to be Indians.

Case Study B. R. Ambedkar

Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar (14 April 1891 – 6 December 1956), also known as Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar or respected father, was an important Indian social reformer who inspired the Dalit Buddhist movement and campaigned against social discrimination towards the untouchables. He was independent India's first law and justice minister, the architect of the Constitution of India, and a founding father of the Republic of India.

Ambedkar was born on 14 April 1891 in Mhow in present-day Madhya Pradesh. He was the 14th and last child of Ramji Maloji Sakpal, an army officer who held the rank of Subedar, and Bhimabai Sakpal, daughter of Laxman Murbadkar. His family was of Marathi background from the village of Ambadawe in Ratnagiri district of Maharashtra. He was born into the low Mahar or Dalit caste, whose members were treated as untouchables and subjected to socio-economic discrimination. Although he attended school, he was segregated and given little attention or help by teachers. They were not even allowed to sit inside the class.

In 1897, Ambedkar's family moved to Mumbai where Ambedkar became the only untouchable enrolled at Elphinstone High School. In 1906, when he was 15 years old, he married a nine-year-old girl, Ramabai.

In 1907, he passed his matriculation examination and in the following year he entered Elphinstone College, which was affiliated to the University of Bombay, becoming the first from his Mahar caste to do so. In 1912, he obtained his degree in economics and political science from Bombay University.

Ambedkar earned doctorates in economics from both Columbia University and the London School of Economics and was well-regarded as a scholar for his research in law, economics, and political science. His Ph.D dissertations were highly regarded. In his early career, he was an economist, professor, and lawyer. In his later life, he was known for his political activities, and played an important role in the founding of the nation. He signed the Poona pact in 1932 in favour of a unified electorate. In 1936, Ambedkar founded the Independent Labour Party, which contested the 1937 Bombay election to the Central Legislative Assembly. Ambedkar won, and was elected to the Bombay Legislative Assembly as a legislator (MLA). Ambedkar published his famous book "Annihilation of Caste" on 15 May 1936. It strongly criticized Hindu orthodox religious leaders and the caste system in general, and chastised Gandhi for his double standards. Ambedkar served on the Defence Advisory Committee and the Viceroy's Executive Council as minister for labour. After the Lahore resolution (1940) of the Muslim League demanding Pakistan, Ambedkar wrote a 400-page book titled "Thoughts on Pakistan", which analyzed the concept of "Pakistan" in all its aspects. In this book, he argued that the Hindus should concede Pakistan to the Muslims.

Upon India's independence on 15 August 1947, the Congress government invited Ambedkar to serve as the nation's first Law and Justice Minister, which he accepted. On 29 August, he was appointed Chairman of the Constitution Drafting Committee, and was appointed by the Constituent Assembly to write India's new Constitution. Ambedkar studied the constitutions of about sixty countries before drafting one for India. Ambedkar is recognized as the "Father of the Constitution of India". The text prepared by Ambedkar provided constitutional guarantees and protections for a wide range of civil liberties for individual citizens, including freedom of religion, the abolition of untouchability, and the outlawing of all forms of discrimination.

Ambedkar studied Buddhism all his life. In 1956, he converted to Buddhism along with many other Dalits. He died six months after conversion due to complications arising from diabetes.

In 1990, he was conferred the Bharat Ratna, India's highest civilian award, posthumously. Ambedkar's legacy includes numerous memorials and depictions in popular culture, and he remains a beacon of hope for Dalits.

Case Study Helen Keller

Born in Alabama, Helen Adams Keller (June 27, 1880 – June 1, 1968) was an American author, and a leading political activist of her day. She had four siblings; two full siblings, and two older half-brothers from her father's prior marriage. Her father, Arthur Henley Keller was an editor of the Tusculum North Alabamian and had served as a captain in the Confederate Army. Her mother, Catherine Everett Keller was the daughter of Charles W. Adams, a Confederate general. Keller contracted an unknown illness at nineteen months old which might have been scarlet fever or meningitis. The illness left her both deaf and blind. Keller learnt to communicate through signs; by the age of seven, Keller had more than sixty home signs to communicate with her family, and could even distinguish people by the vibration of their footsteps.

In May 1888, Keller started attending the Perkins Institute for the Blind. In 1894, she moved to New York to attend the Wright-Humason School for the Deaf, and to learn from Sarah Fuller at the Horace Mann

School for the Deaf. In 1896, Keller entered The Cambridge School for Young Ladies before being admitted to Radcliffe College of Harvard University. Anne Sullivan, herself visually impaired, became Keller's instructor. It was the beginning of a 49-year-long relationship during which Sullivan became Keller's governess and eventually her companion. Helen Keller was isolated but was still in touch with the outside world. She enjoyed music by feeling the beat and had a strong connection with animals through touch. Keller learned to speak and spent much of her life giving speeches and lectures on aspects of her life. She learned to hear people's speech by reading their lips with her hands. She also became proficient at using braille and reading sign language with her hands.

She was the first deaf-blind person to earn a Bachelor of Arts degree. The story of Keller was made famous by Keller's autobiography, "The Story of My Life", which led to adaptations for film and stage.

She was a prolific author, and was well-traveled and outspoken in her convictions. A member of the Socialist Party of America and the Industrial Workers of the World, she campaigned for women's suffrage, labor rights, socialism, and other similar causes. Keller visited thirty-five countries from 1946 to 1957. In 1948 she went to New Zealand and visited deaf schools in Christchurch and Auckland. Keller suffered a series of strokes in 1961 and spent the last years of her life at her home. Keller devoted much of her later life to raising funds for the American Foundation for the Blind. On September 14, 1964, President Lyndon B. Johnson awarded her the Presidential Medal of Freedom, one of the United States' highest civilian honors. In 1965, she was elected to the National Women's Hall of Fame. She was inducted into the Alabama Women's Hall of Fame in 1971.

She died in her sleep on June 1, 1968, at her home in Connecticut, a few weeks before her eighty-eighth birthday. She was buried at the Washington National Cathedral in Washington, D.C.

Case Study Sentinelese

The Sentinelese, also known as the North Sentinel Islanders, are an indigenous people who inhabit North Sentinel Island in the Bay of Bengal in India. The island lies off the southwest coast of South Andaman Island, about 64 km west of Andaman capital Port Blair. It has an area of about 59.67 km² and a roughly square outline. They are considered one of the world's last uncontacted peoples. Designated a Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Group and a Scheduled Tribe, they belong to the class of Andamanese people. Along with the Great Andamanese, the Jarawas, the Onge, the Shompen, and the Nicobarese, the Sentinelese are one of the tribal populations of the Andaman and Nicobar Islands. The Sentinelese have refused any interaction with the outside world, and must rank as the most isolated tribe on earth. The Sentinelese have been widely described as a Stone Age tribe, with some reports claiming they have lived in isolation for over 60,000 years. They are considered one of the world's last uncontacted peoples. They are hostile to outsiders and have killed anyone who have dared to approach the island. In 1956, the Government of India declared North Sentinel Island a tribal reserve and prohibited travel within 4.8 km of it. It further maintains a constant armed patrol to prevent intrusions by outsiders. Photography is also prohibited.

Estimates of the group's size range between 15 and 500. The Onge call North Sentinel Island Chia daa Kwokweyeh. It is not known what they call themselves.

The Sentinelese have dark skin and are shorter in stature than average humans. One report described a man as 1.6 metres (5 ft 3 in) tall, possibly because of insular dwarfism, nutrition, or simply genetic heritage. Other researchers have estimated their height to be between 5 ft 3 in (1.60 m) and 5 ft 5 in (1.65 m) and recorded their skin colour as "dark, shining black".

The Sentinelese are hunter-gatherers. They use bows and arrows to hunt terrestrial wildlife and rudimentary methods to catch local seafood. Most of their practices have not evolved beyond the Stone Age; they do not engage in agriculture. It is unclear whether they have any knowledge of making fire either though some believe they do.

They share similarities with the Onge people in cooking styles, in body decoration and material culture. There are also similarities in the design of their canoes. Similarities with the Jarawas have been also noted. Both tribes sleep on the ground, while the Onge sleep on raised platforms. The Sentinelese live in temporary huts erected on poles with leaf-covered roofs. They scavenged metal from wrecks to create tools and weapons too. They have also developed canoes for fishing but use poles propel them.

Nothing is known about the Sentinelese language. There is uncertainty about the similarity with the Onge and Jarawa languages, if any. The Anthropological Survey of India's 2016 handbook on Vulnerable Tribe Groups considers them to be mutually unintelligible.

The first recorded sighting was in 1771 by a ship which saw lights on the shore, and the first recorded contact was in 1867 when the Indian merchant-vessel *Nineveh* foundered on the reef off North Sentinel.

In 1880, in an effort to establish contact with the Sentinelese, British naval officer Maurice Vidal Portman, led a group of Europeans to North Sentinel Island. Portman's men captured six individuals, an elderly man and woman and four children. The man and woman died shortly after their arrival in Port Blair and the children sickened. Portman sent the children back to the North Sentinel Island with gifts to establish friendly contact. In 1896, a convict escaped from the penal colony on Great Andaman Island on a makeshift raft and drifted across to the North Sentinel beach. His body was discovered by a search party some days later with arrows and a cut throat

MCC Bonnington, a British official, visited the island in 1911 and 1932 to conduct a census. There have been other recorded instances of British administrators visiting the island, including Rogers in 1902, but none of the expeditions after 1880 had any ethnographic purpose. In 1954, Italian explorer Lidio Cipriani visited the island but did not come across any inhabitants.

In 1977, *MV Rusley* ran aground on the North Sentinel Reefs. On 2 August 1981, the cargo ship *Primrose*, carrying cargo between Australia and Bangladesh, ran aground in rough seas just off North Sentinel Island, stranding a small crew. The Sentinelese scoured the abandoned shipwrecks to salvage iron for their weaponry.

In 1967, a group of 20 people, were led by T. N. Pandit, an anthropologist working for the Anthropological Survey of India, to North Sentinel Island to explore it and befriend the Sentinelese. During the 1970s and 1980s, Pandit undertook several visits to the island, sometimes as an "expert advisor" in tour parties including dignitaries who wished to encounter an aboriginal tribe. Beginning in 1981, he regularly led official expeditions with the purpose of establishing friendly

contact. Many of these got a friendly reception, with hordes of gifts left for them, but some ended in violent encounters, which were mostly suppressed.

In early 1974, a National Geographic film crew went to the island with a team of anthropologists (including Pandit), accompanied by armed police, to film a documentary, "Man in Search of Man". In 1991, the first instances of peaceful contact were recorded in the course of two routine expeditions by an Indian anthropological team consisting of government representatives and Madhumala Chattopadhyay.

During a 4 January 1991 visit, the Sentinelese approached the party without weaponry for the first time. They collected coconuts that were offered and approached quite close to the dinghies for the first time. The Director of Tribal Welfare distributed five bags of coconuts hand-to-hand.

In 2014, an aerial expedition followed by a circumnavigation investigated the effects of a forest fire. Important data was gathered and the expedition recorded that the fire did not seem to have affected the populace.

On 27 January 2006, Indian fishermen Sunder Raj and Pandit Tiwari, who had been attempting to illegally harvest crabs off North Sentinel Island, drifted towards the island after their boat's makeshift anchor failed during the night. They did not respond to warning calls from passing fishermen, and their boat drifted into the shallows near the island, where a group of Sentinelese warriors attacked the boat and killed the fishermen with axes.

In November 2018 a Christian missionary organization "All Nations" sent John Allen Chau, a 26-year-old American, to make contact with the Sentinelese to convert them to Christianity. Chau traveled illegally to the island by bribing local fishermen. On 15 November Chau attempted his first visit in a fishing boat. On his final visit, on 17 November, Chau instructed the fishermen to leave without him. The fishermen later saw the islanders dragging Chau's body, and the next day they saw his body on the shore.

This case study reinforces the importance of collective identity which may or may not change with the passage of time. On the other hand, the culture of other tribes has changed rapidly, and they have assimilated with other populations. The reluctance of the Sentinelese may be attributed to the fear of cultural loss, or annihilation by disease. This then defines most aspects of their culture.

Case Study Hutu tutsi

The Genocide against the Tutsi in Rwanda, was a mass slaughter in [Rwanda](#), which took place in 1994 during the Rwandan Civil War. This was the culmination of decades of strife between the Tutsis and the Hutu. The Belgian rulers also discriminated between the two groups, preferring the Tutsis to the Hutus. Thus, the Tutsis were given superior jobs and benefits. After Rwanda got independence in 1962, the Hutus tried to take power, and marginalize the Tutsis.

The genocide was organized by members of the core Hutu political elite, many of whom occupied positions at top levels of the national government. A genocide against the Tutsi had been planned since 1993. Genocidal killings began after the assassination of Rwandan president Juvenal Habyarimana in 1994 when soldiers, police, and militia executed key Tutsi and moderate Hutu leaders. Some people blame the new president Paul Kagame for the attacks.

The scale and brutality of the massacre caused shock worldwide, even though Western nations largely ignored it. Most of the victims were killed in their own villages, and by their neighbors and fellow villagers. Hutu gangs searched for victims in churches and school buildings. An estimated 500,000 to 1,000,000 Rwandans were killed, about seventy percent of the Tutsi population. The genocide ended with the military victory of the Rwandan Patriotic Front.

The genocide had lasting and profound effects on Rwanda and neighbouring countries. Today, Rwanda has two public holidays to mourn the genocide, and denial of the genocide is an offence. After the genocide, nations collaborated to establish the International Criminal Court.

This is a manifestation of ethnic pride and polarization to the extreme, and the fact that a single event can bring simmering tensions to the forefront. This is in spite of the fact that the two groups speak the same language, follow the same customs and live in the same areas. This also shows meddling by an external agency- the Belgians- which led to unrest.

Case Study Rohingya

The Rohingya people are an ethnic minority who live in the northern region of Rakhine State, Myanmar, and rank as one of the world's most persecuted minorities. They consider themselves to be descendants of Arab traders who settled in the region many generations ago.

The Rohingya conflict was a conflict in northern Rakhine State, Myanmar characterized by violence between the Rohingya Muslim and Rakhine Buddhist communities, a military crackdown on Rohingya civilians by Myanmar's security forces, and militant attacks by Rohingya insurgents in townships bordering Bangladesh.

The conflict arose from religious differences between Rakhine Buddhists and Rohingya Muslims. During World War II in Burma, Rohingya Muslims, who were allied with the British and were promised a Muslim state in return, fought Rakhine Buddhists, who were allied with the Japanese. After independence in 1948, the government of the country denied citizenship to the Rohingyas, subjecting them to discrimination. Muslims fled from Japanese-controlled and Buddhist-majority regions to Muslim-dominated northern Arakan with many being killed. In return, a "reverse ethnic cleansing" was carried out. The Muslim attacks caused the Buddhists to flee to southern Arakan. In May 1946, Muslim leaders from Arakan, Burma met Muhammad Ali Jinnah, the founder of Pakistan, and asked for the annexation of two townships in the Mayu region, but Jinnah could not interfere as this was an internal matter. The Rohingyas were denied citizenship in 1982 by the government of Myanmar, which saw them as illegal immigrants from Bangladesh.

From 1947 to 1961, Rohingya mujahideen fought government forces for autonomy or secession, so that it could be annexed by East Pakistan. The mujahideen eventually lost most of its momentum and support, and were marginalized. In the 1970s, new Rohingya separatist movements emerged, and the fighting culminated with the Burmese government launching a massive military operation in 1978 to expel foreigners. In the 1990s, the Rohingya Solidarity Organization (RSO) relaunched attacks on Burmese authorities. The Burmese government responded militarily with "Operation Clean and Beautiful Nation", but failed to disarm the RSO.

In October 2016, Burmese border posts were attacked by a new insurgent group, Harakah al-Yaqin, resulting in the deaths of at least 40 people. Violence erupted again in November 2016, bringing the 2016 death toll to 134, and again on 25 August 2017, when the Arakan Rohingya Salvation Army launched attacks on police posts and an army base that left 71 dead.

The Office of the U.N. High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) released a report in 2017 detailing the Burmese military's efforts to drive away hundreds of thousands of Rohingyas from Myanmar and expel them from their territory. As a result, more than 600,000 refugees fled to Bangladesh by 2017. On 22 May 2018, Amnesty International released a report claiming that ARSA killed as many as 99 Hindu civilians in 2017. An August 2018 study by Harvard University estimated that 24,000 Rohingyas had been killed, 18,000 Rohingya women and girls had been raped, 116,000 Rohingyas had been tortured, and 36,000 Rohingyas had been victims of arson. This is a case where ethnic identity is seen as being much more important than national identity, and there is a clear dislike for Rohingya Muslims among Buddhists.

Case Study Velupillai Prabhakaran

Thiruvankadam Velupillai (26 November 1954 – 19 May 2009) was the founder and leader of the Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam (the LTTE or the Tamil Tigers), a militant organization that sought to create an independent Tamil state in the north and east of Sri Lanka.

Velupillai Prabhakaran was born in the northern coastal town of Valvettithurai on 26 November 1954, as the youngest of four children to Thiruvankadam Velupillai and his wife Vallipuram Parvathy. Thiruvankadam Velupillai was the District Land Officer in the Ceylon Government. His family was wealthy and owned and managed major Hindu temples in Valvettithurai. Prabhakaran was fascinated by Napoleon and Alexander the Great. He was also highly influenced by prominent Indian nationalists Subhas Chandra Bose and Bhagat Singh who fought the British Empire. Prabhakaran never developed a systematic philosophy, but clearly stated that his goal was 'Revolutionary socialism and the creation of an egalitarian society'.

Angered by discrimination against Tamil people by the Sri Lankan government, he joined the student group Tamil Youth Front (TYF) and founded the Tamil New Tigers (TNT) as a successor to organizations that protested the discrimination of Tamils. In 1975, he carried out the first major political assassination by a Tamil group, killing the mayor of Jaffna, Alfred Duraiappah, by shooting him at Ponnaalai. In the early 1970s, United Front government of Sirimavo Bandaranaike introduced the Policy of standardization which made the criteria for university admission lower for the Sinhalese than for the Tamils. Prabhakaran dropped out of school and got associated with the Kuttimani-Thangathurai group formed by Selvarajah Yogachandran and Nadarajah Thangathurai.

He founded the LTTE in 1976, which fought for several years to create an independent state for the Sri Lankan Tamil people. The LTTE rose to prominence in 1983 after they ambushed a patrol of the Sri Lanka Army outside Jaffna, resulting in the deaths of 13 soldiers and marking the beginning of the Sri Lankan Civil War. The LTTE controlled large swathes of land in the north and east of the country, running a de facto state with Prabhakaran as its leader. The Sri Lanka Army launched a military campaign to defeat the Tamil Tigers in 2006.

The LTTE were allegedly involved in the assassination of Rajiv Gandhi, the ex-prime minister of India in 1991, which they denied involvement and alleged the event as an international conspiracy against them.

Prabhakaran and his son Charles Anthony were killed in fighting with the Sri Lankan Army in May 2009. His wife's and daughter's bodies were found by the Sri Lankan army and his 12-year-old second son was executed a short time later.

Case Study Fidel Castro

Fidel Alejandro Castro Ruz (13 August 1926 – 25 November 2016) was a Cuban communist revolutionary and politician who served the Republic of Cuba as Prime Minister from 1959 to 1976 and as President from 1976 to 2008. A Marxist–Leninist and Cuban nationalist by ideology and conviction, Castro also served as the First Secretary of the Communist Party of Cuba from 1961 to 2011. Under his administration, Cuba became a one-party communist state, while industry and business were nationalized and state socialist ideals were implemented throughout society.

Born in Biran, Oriente as the son of a wealthy Spanish farmer in 1926, Castro adopted leftist anti-imperialist politics while studying law at the University of Havana. After participating in rebellions against right-wing governments in the Dominican Republic and Colombia, he planned the overthrow of Cuban President Fulgencio Batista, launching a failed attack on the Moncada Barracks in 1953. After a year's imprisonment, Castro traveled to Mexico where he formed a revolutionary group, the 26th of July Movement, with his brother Raul Castro and Che Guevara. Returning to Cuba, Castro played an important role in the Cuban Revolution by leading the Movement in a guerrilla war against Batista's forces. After Batista's overthrow in 1959, Castro assumed military and political power as Cuba's Prime Minister. The United States opposed Castro's government and attempted to remove him by assassination, economic blockade and counter-revolution, carrying out the Bay of Pigs Invasion in 1961. Castro aligned with the Soviet Union and allowed the Soviets to place nuclear weapons in Cuba, leading to the Cuban Missile Crisis in 1962.

Castro adopted a Marxist–Leninist model of development, and converted Cuba into a one-party, socialist state under Communist Party rule, the first in the Western Hemisphere. Policies introducing central economic planning and expanding healthcare and education were accompanied by state control of the press and the suppression of internal dissent. The longest-serving non-royal head of state in the 20th and 21st centuries, Castro polarized world opinion. His supporters saw him as a champion of socialism and anti-imperialism whose revolutionary regime advanced economic and social justice while securing Cuba's independence from American imperialism. Critics viewed him as a dictator whose administration oversaw human-rights abuses and the impoverishment of the country's economy. Castro was decorated with various international awards and significantly influenced different individuals and groups across the world.

Case Study Karl Marx

Karl Marx (5 May 1818 – 14 March 1883) was a influential German philosopher, economist, sociologist, political theorist, and socialist revolutionary of the Nineteenth century.

Born in Trier, Germany, Marx went on to specialize in law and philosophy. The third of nine children, Marx was privately educated by his father until 1830, when he entered Trier High School. In October 1835 at the age of 17, Marx travelled to the University of Bonn to study philosophy and literature, but his father preferred law. At the University at Bonn, he joined the Poets' Club, a group containing political radicals that were monitored by the police. His father then transferred him to the University of Berlin. Marx attended lectures of Eduard Gans and of Karl von Savigny who influenced him greatly. Although studying law, he was fascinated by philosophy and looked for a way to combine the two. Marx also became interested in the German philosopher G.W.F. Hegel. He became involved with a group of radical thinkers known as the Young Hegelians in 1837. They gathered around Ludwig Feuerbach and Bruno Bauer.

He married Jenny von Westphalen in 1843. Due to his political publications, Marx became stateless and lived in exile with his wife and children in London for decades, where he continued to develop his thoughts in collaboration with German thinker Friedrich Engels who published most of his writings. His best-known titles are the 1848 pamphlet, *The Communist Manifesto*, and the three-volume *Das Kapital*. His political and philosophical thought had enormous influence on subsequent intellectual, economic and political history, and his name has become a household word in many countries.

Marx's critical theories about society, economics and politics—known as Marxism—hold that human societies develop through class struggle. In capitalism, this manifests itself in the conflict between the ruling classes (Bourgeoisie) that control the means of production and the working classes (Proletariat) who sell their labour in return for wages. Employing an approach called historical materialism, Marx predicted that capitalism produced internal tensions which would lead to its self-destruction and replacement by a new system: socialism.

Marx engaged in an intensive study of political economy after reading the works of authors such as Adam Smith, David Ricardo, James Mill, and others. He also studied political economy and this resulted in his major economic work—the three-volume series called *Capital* which described the working of Marxism. Marx also wrote *The Economic and Philosophical Manuscripts*. These manuscripts covered numerous topics, detailing Marx's concept of alienated labour. These books laid the foundation for Marx and Engels's most famous work, a political pamphlet that is known as *The Communist Manifesto*. *The Communist Manifesto* was first published on 21 February 1848. *The Communist Manifesto* laid out the beliefs of the new Communist League.

Marx moved to London in early June 1849 and would remain based in the city for the rest of his life. In 1859, Marx published *A Contribution to the Critique of Political Economy*, his first serious economic work. This work was intended merely as a preview of his three-volume *Das Kapital* (English title: *Capital: Critique of Political Economy*), which he intended to publish at a later date. In *A Contribution to the Critique of Political Economy*, Marx expanded on the labour theory of value advocated by David Ricardo. The work was well received, and sold out quickly. The success of *A Contribution to the Critique of Political Economy* stimulated Marx in the early 1860s to publish three large volumes that would compose his major life's work—*Das Kapital* and the *Theories of Surplus Value*. In 1867, the first volume of *Das Kapital* was published. Here Marx elaborated his labour theory of value, which had been influenced by Thomas Hodgskin. Volumes II and III of *Capital* remained manuscripts upon which Marx

continued to work for the rest of his life. Both volumes were published by Engels after Marx's death. During the last decade of his life, Marx's health declined and so did his output. Before he died, Marx asked Engels to write his ideas on family and property, which were published in 1884 under the title "The Origin of the Family, Private Property and the State".

His work was influenced by the inequality and suffering he saw in his life. His work was also a product of his times and highly reactionary. It was also Eurocentric. It was only in his work "The Asiatic modes of production", that he attempted to give his work an international twist.

Case Study D N Jha

Dwijendra Narayan Jha (born 1940) is an Indian historian, specialising in ancient and medieval India. He was a professor of history at Delhi University and is a member of the Indian Council of Historical Research. Jha completed his BA (Hons.) in History at Presidency College of the University of Calcutta and then his MA in History at Patna University where he was a student of Professor R.S. Sharma.

Jha has criticized Hindu nationalist ideology and its rewriting of history, and the "communalism" and "saffronisation", which took place during the 1998 to 2004 Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) government of the Republic of India. He is also critical of the view that "tolerance is the very essence of Hinduism", and what he regards as Brahmanical intolerance in ancient India, even though he is himself a Maithili Brahmin.

Jha has received death threats over his book *The Myth of the Holy Cow* in which he states that eating beef in ancient India was common and is evidenced by Vedic and Post-Vedic texts. His book caused much controversy, and offended the feelings of many Hindus.

Arun Shourie accused Jha of distortion of the facts in the destruction of Nalanda University by Islamic invaders in 12th Century AD. Shourie accused Jha of selective usage of sources, and bias. In an article in the Indian Express, Jha stated that Shourie was distorting what he had said, and that Shourie's allegations of plagiarism are baseless. Jha also criticized Shourie's book *Eminent Historians*, saying that it contains "slander" and "has nothing to do with history." Jha's works are seen as examples dogmatic Marxist historiography, and he is seen as being biased and prejudiced to the extreme. His work is cited as an example where ideology is allowed to interfere with a balanced presentation of facts, and his ideology is allowed to dictate personal identity.

Case Study Martin Luther King

Martin Luther King Jr was arguably America's most important civil rights activists. His non-violent protests helped to raise awareness of racial inequalities in America, leading to significant political change. Martin Luther King was also an eloquent orator who won hearts of people, both blacks and whites included.

Martin Luther King, Jr. was born in Atlanta in 1929. His father and grandfather were pastors in an African-American Baptist church. King attended segregated schooling in Atlanta and then went to study in Pennsylvania and Boston University. During his time at University, Martin Luther King became aware of the vast inequality and injustice faced by black Americans; he was influenced by Gandhi's philosophy

of non-violent protest. He combined the philosophy of Gandhi with the teachings of his Baptist faith. After getting married, King became a pastor in Montgomery, Alabama.

A turning point in his life was the Montgomery Bus Boycott which became a turning point in the civil rights struggle.

In 1955, Rosa Parks, a civil rights activist, refused to give up her seat – she was sitting in a white-only seat in a bus. Martin Luther King organized a strike where coloured people refused to use the city buses. The boycott lasted for several months, and the issue was brought to the Supreme Court which declared that the segregation was unconstitutional.

After the success of the Montgomery bus boycott, King founded the Southern Christian Leadership Conference (SCLC). This was a nucleus for the growing civil rights movement. The 1960s saw the rise of the Black power movement, epitomized by Malcolm X and other black nationalist groups. However, King always remained committed to the ideals of non-violent struggle.

Martin Luther King was an inspirational and influential speaker; he had the capacity to move and uplift his audiences. He captured the injustice of the time but could also offer a vision of hope.. His speeches were largely free of revenge, instead focusing on the need to move forward. He was named as Man of the Year by Time magazine in 1963, it followed his famous “I Have a Dream Speech” – delivered in Washington during a civil rights march.

In 1964, Martin Luther King was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize for his work towards social justice. King announced he would turn over the prize money to the civil rights movement. With the prestige of the Nobel Prize, King was increasingly consulted by politicians such as Lyndon Johnson.

On April 4th, 1968, King was assassinated one day after he had delivered his final speech “I’ve Been to the Mountaintop”

In his honour, America has instigated a national Martin Luther King Day. He remains symbolic of America’s fight for justice and racial equality.

Case Study Christopher Columbus

Christopher Columbus(1451–1506) was an Italian explorer, colonizer, and navigator. He is remembered as the principal European discoverer of the Americas and laid the framework for the later European colonization of North and South America.

Christopher Columbus was born in the Republic of Genoa, in Northwestern Italy. His father was a middle-class merchant. Columbus learnt to sail from an early age and later worked as a business agent, travelling around Europe to England, Ireland and the West coast of Africa. He studied astronomy, science and navigation and was fluent in Latin, Portuguese and Spanish. Christopher Columbus knew the earth was spherical at a time when most still thought the world was flat. An ambitious man, Christopher Columbus hoped to find a Western trade route to the lucrative spice markets in Asia. Rather than sailing East, he hoped that sailing west would lead to countries like Japan and China.

Columbus' first voyage was completed in 1492. He had intended to sail to Japan, but ended up in the Bahamas, which he named San Salvador. Columbus made a total of four journeys, where he sailed around the Caribbean islands of Cuba, Jamaica, the Bahamas and also to the mainland America.

Columbus was not the first person to reach America. Previous successful voyages included a Norse expedition led by Leif Ericson. However, Columbus was the first to travel to America and establish permanent settlements. Columbus' voyages and reports, over the next 400 years encouraged all the major European powers to seek to colonize parts of America.

Columbus died in 1506, from a heart attack. He is known as the man who put the Americas on the map. Columbus Day is observed on 12 October in Spain and in the Americas.

Case Study Charles Darwin

Charles Darwin (1809 – 1882) was an English Natural scientist who proposed the theory of evolution – a theory which states that Man evolved from lower life forms. At the time, his work was regarded as controversial, but his theory of evolution and natural selection later became accepted within the scientific community.

Charles Darwin was born on 12 February 1809 in Shrewsbury, Shropshire. He was born into a wealthy and influential family. His grandfather was Erasmus Darwin, one of the leading intellectuals of 18th century England.

Darwin wanted to study medicine at Edinburgh University, but eventually studied Divinity at Christ's College, Cambridge University. Darwin was not a great student, and spent a great deal of time in studying nature; Due to his interests in natural science, Darwin was offered a place on an expedition aboard the HMS Beagle.

At the time, religion was a powerful force in society, and most people took the Bible as the infallible, literal word of God. People thought God created the world in seven days, and the world was only a few thousand years old. However, Darwin soon realized that life was much older. On the voyage, Darwin made notes about specimens he found on his voyages. In particular, at the Galapagos Islands, Darwin was struck by how the Finch was different on each individual island. He noticed that the Finch had somehow adapted to the various aspects of the particular island.

Darwin eventually came up with a more detailed theory of natural selection and gradual evolution and diversification of species over time.

Darwin continued to develop his theory, but, realizing how controversial his ideas were, Darwin delayed publishing them. However, after learning that another naturalist, Alfred Russel Wallace had developed similar ideas, that Darwin felt confident about publishing his own book.

In 1859, the ground-breaking 'On the Origin of Species by Means of Natural Selection' was published. It immediately gained widespread interest and attention, leading to intense debate about the contention that man – by implication was descended from animals like the ape.

However, by the time he died in 1882, his ideas had become widely accepted by the scientific and non-religious community. This is an example of how religious and cultural identity can be impacted through scientific work. This offers a ray of hope for developing countries, where dogma still rule the roost.

Case Study Mother Teresa

Mother Teresa (1910–1997) was a Roman Catholic nun who devoted her life to serving the poor and destitute in Calcutta, India where she founded the Missionaries of Charity, a religious order devoted to helping the downtrodden. In 1979, Mother Teresa was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 2016, was canonized by the Roman Catholic Church as Saint Teresa.

Mother Teresa was born in 1910 in the Republic of Macedonia. At a young age, she felt a calling to be a nun and serve the poor. At the age of 18, she joined a group of nuns in Ireland. After a few months of training, with the Sisters of Loreto, she travelled to India. She took her formal religious vows in 1931 and was named after St Therese of Lisieux – the patron saint of missionaries.

After arriving in India, she began working as a teacher; however, the widespread poverty of Calcutta made a lasting and deep impression on her, and this led to her starting a new order called "The Missionaries of Charity". The primary objective of this mission was to look after people, who nobody else was prepared to look after.

She experienced two particularly traumatic periods in Calcutta. The first was the Bengal famine of 1943 and the second was the Hindu/Muslim violence in 1946, before the partition of India. In 1948, she left the convent to live full-time among the poorest of Calcutta. She chose to wear a white Indian sari, with a blue border, out of respect for the traditional Indian dress. For many years, Mother Teresa and her nuns survived on minimal income and food, with minimal funds. But, slowly her efforts were appreciated by the local community and Indian politicians.

In 1952, she opened her first home for the dying, which allowed people to die with dignity. Mother Teresa often spent time with those who were dying. Her work spread around the world. By 2013, there were 700 missions operating in over 130 countries. The scope of their work also expanded to include orphanages and hospices for those with terminal illnesses.

Mother Teresa never sought to convert those of another faith. Those in her hospices were given the religious rites appropriate to their faith. However, she had a very firm Catholic faith and took a strict line on abortion, the death penalty and divorce – even if her position was unpopular. Her whole life was influenced by her faith and religion, even though at times she confessed she didn't feel the presence of God.

In 1979, she was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize “for work undertaken in the struggle to overcome poverty and distress, which also constitutes a threat to peace.” She didn’t attend the ceremonial banquet but asked that the \$192,000 fund be given to the poor.

In later years, she was more active in western developed countries. She commented that though the West was materially prosperous, there was often a spiritual poverty.

Over the last two decades of her life, Mother Teresa suffered various health problems, but nothing could dissuade her from fulfilling her mission of serving the poor and needy. Until her very last illness she was active in travelling around the world to the different branches of The Missionaries of Charity. Following Mother Teresa’s death, the Vatican began the process of beatification, which is the second step on the way to canonization and sainthood. Mother Teresa was formally beatified in October 2003 by Pope John Paul II.

Mother Teresa was a living saint who offered a great example and inspiration to the world. This is a shining example of how an individual can rise above national barriers. However, some people have questioned her religious neutrality.

Case Study Dalai Lama

The 14th Dalai Lama was born Lhamo Dondrub, into a large family in the village of Qinghai, China. At the age of two, he was picked out as the rebirth of the thirteenth Dalai Lama and sent for formal monastic training to become a Buddhist monk and the spiritual head of the Tibetan people. His spiritual name is Tenzin Gatos, but is mostly referred to as the ‘Dalai Lama’

He was formally enthroned as the Dalai Lama in 1950, shortly after the Chinese invasion of Tibet and became both spiritual and political leader to a country under invasion and occupation.

After several years of Chinese occupation and persecution of the Tibetan people, the Dalai Lama fled over the border into India. After meeting with the prime minister of India, [Jawaharlal Nehru](#), the Dalai Lama and up to 80,000 Tibetan exiles set up a government in exile in Dharamshala, India.

The Dalai Lama has followed a long campaign of non-violent resistance to the Chinese occupation. He has frequently called on the Chinese to respect the basic human rights of the indigenous Tibetans and end the migration of the ethnic Han Chinese into Tibet. In 1987 he proposed a five-point peace plan about the future of Tibet and called Tibet to be made into a zone of peace. He also secured United Nations resolutions to support the right for Tibetan self-determination.

He has also taught extensively on Buddhist philosophy, and symbolized love , truth and peace.

As a monk, he follows a celibate lifestyle. He rises early every morning for meditation and prayer. He is a vegetarian and encourages others to adopt a vegetarian diet.

The Dalai Lama has met with many representatives of different religions. The Dalai Lama has been keen to stress the underlying unity of different religions; he has even said he is not keen to convert people to Buddhism.

He said Pope John Paul II was sympathetic to his plight, even though he was reluctant to antagonize the Chinese because of the plight of Catholics in China.

The Dalai Lama was awarded the Nobel Prize for peace in 1989.

He has remained active until his later years, frequently travelling around the world to talk on Buddhism and issues relating to human rights. He has sought to develop a meaningful relationship between Buddhism and science. The Dalai Lama has also spoken out about the importance of protecting the environment, avoiding war, the benefits of nuclear disarmament and has been critical of the worst excesses of capitalism. He is a shining example of inter-faith harmony and dialogue, and how religious identity can be neutralized through better education and awareness.

Case Study Stephen Hawking

Stephen Hawking (1942 – 2018) is an English theoretical physicist, cosmologist and author. He is known for his attempts to explain in clear terms the origins of the universe and some of the most complicated aspects of the cosmos and physics to the layman in easily understandable language. Hawking was the first scientist to offer a theory of cosmology explained by a union of the general theory of relativity and quantum mechanics.

Stephen William Hawking was born on 8 January 1942 in Oxford, England. His family moved to Oxford to escape the threat of WW2 attacks over London. As a child, he was noted to be incredibly prodigious and highly talented. After leaving school, he got a place at University College, Oxford University where he studied Physics.

After gaining a B.A.Hons in Physics, he briefly stayed to study astronomy but was not interested in it so he moved to Trinity College, Cambridge where he pursued his passion for theoretical astronomy and cosmology.

It was in Cambridge that Stephen Hawking first started to develop symptoms of neuro-muscular problems – a type of motor neuron disease. This started to hamper his physical movements. His speech became slurred, and he became unable to even to feed himself. At one stage, the doctors gave him a lifespan of three years. However, the progress of the disease slowed down, and he has managed to overcome his severe disability to continue his research and active public engagements. At Cambridge, a fellow scientist developed a synthetic speech device which enabled him to speak by using a touchpad. This early synthetic speech sound has become the ‘voice’ of Stephen Hawking, and as a result, he has kept the original sound of this early model – despite technological advancements.

Stephen Hawking’s principal fields of research have been involved in theoretical cosmology and quantum gravity.

Amongst many other achievements, he developed a mathematical model for Albert Einstein’s General Theory of Relativity. He has also undertaken a lot of work on the nature of the Universe, The Big Bang and Black Holes.

In 1974, he outlined his theory that black holes leak energy and fade away to nothing. This became known as “Hawking radiation” in 1974. He demonstrated that Einstein’s General Theory of Relativity implies space and time would have a beginning in the Big Bang and an end in black holes.

Despite being one of the best physicists of his generation, he has also been able to translate difficult physics models into a general understanding for the general public. His books – A Brief History of Time and The Universe in A Nutshell have become bestsellers – with a Brief History of Time staying in the Bestsellers lists for over 230 weeks and selling over 10 million copies. In his books, Hawking tries to explain scientific concepts in everyday language and give an overview to the workings behind the cosmos. Stephen Hawking has become one of the most famous scientists of his generation. He makes frequent public engagements and has portrayed himself in popular media culture from programmes, such as The Simpsons to Star Trek.

In the late 1990s, he was reportedly offered a knighthood, but declined it.

Stephen Hawking passed away on 14 March 2018 at his home in Cambridge due to natural causes.

He had stated, “If we do discover a complete theory, it should in time be understandable in broad principle by everyone, not just a few scientists. Then we shall all, philosophers, scientists, and just ordinary people, be able to take part in the discussion of the question of why it is that we and the universe exist. If we find the answer to that, it would be the ultimate triumph of human reason — for then we would know the mind of God.”

This is a prime example of how an individual communicates his scientific ideas clearly to the masses. These can help usher in a scientific revolution indirectly, lead to convergence of thoughts and ideas, neutralizing identity.

Case Study Winston Churchill

Sir Winston Churchill (30 November 1874 – 24 January 1965) was a British politician and author, best known as Prime Minister of the United Kingdom during the Second World War when his country emerged victorious.

Winston was born near Oxford to an aristocratic family – the Duke of Marlborough. He spent most of his childhood at boarding school – Harrow. Churchill wasn’t the best student, due to his rebellious nature and was slow to learn; but Churchill excelled at sports and joined the officer cadet corps.

On leaving school, he went to Sandhurst to train as an officer. Churchill wanted to gain as much active military experience as possible. He used his mother’s connections to get postings to areas of conflict. The young Churchill received postings to Cuba and North West India. He also combined his military duties with working as a war correspondent – earning substantial money for his reports on the fighting.

In 1899, he resigned from the military and pursued his career as a war correspondent, and was in South Africa for the Boer War.

Churchill returned to the UK in 1900 and became an MP. In 1904, he left the Conservative Party and joined the Liberal Party. In the Liberal Party, he rose through the ranks quickly. However, although Churchill was a Liberal, he was also anti-Socialist and distrusted trade unions. During the General Strike, he took a hardline stance to defeat the unions at any cost.

In 1911, he was made First Lord of the Admiralty – a post he held into the First World War. On the outbreak of hostilities in Europe, Churchill was one of the most strident members of the cabinet arguing for British involvement in the war. Churchill also used naval funds to help develop the tank – something he felt would be useful in the war.

Churchill later joined Lloyd George's coalition government. In 1917, Churchill was made Minister of Munitions – a job requiring strong administrative skills to manage limited resources during the war. Churchill was considered an efficient and skilled minister.

At the end of the First World War, Churchill was active in trying to support the Russian white army – who were trying to resist the Communist forces which had gained control over the Soviet Union.

In 1924 Churchill was appointed as Chancellor of the Exchequer by PM Stanley Baldwin. Churchill returned Britain to the Gold Standard at a pre-war level. The low growth and declining living standards contributed to the General Strike of 1926 – Churchill tried to break the strikers and defeat the trades unions.

Churchill spoke about the growing danger of Hitler. He also opposed Indian Independence and was a staunch supporter of the Empire.

After an unsuccessful start to the Second World War, the Commons chose Churchill to lead the UK in a national coalition. Churchill was instrumental in insisting Britain keep fighting. Churchill was a capable and efficient war leader. Churchill was involved in many aspects of the war, taking an interest in all areas, especially the build up to the D-Day landings in Normandy. Churchill also participated in conferences with Stalin and Roosevelt which helped shape the war and post-war settlement.

It was Churchill who helped popularise the phrase 'Iron Curtain' after he saw the growing gulf between the Communist East and Western Europe.

After winning the Second World War, Churchill was shocked to lose the 1945 general election to a resurgent Labour party. He was Leader of the Opposition from 1945-51.

But, under the Conservatives, he returned to power in the 1950 election – accepting much of the post-war consensus and the end of the British Empire. Churchill served as PM from 1951-55 before retiring from politics.

Churchill was awarded the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1953. Towards the end of his life, Churchill also became a very accomplished artist. Churchill died in his home at age 90, on 24 January 1965. His funeral was the largest state funeral in the world, until that date.

Although praised in many western circles, he was an avowed racist. His inaction led to millions of deaths during the Bengal famine of 1943. He wanted to prolong the British Raj at any cost. He was proud of his national, linguistic and racial identity, and came to be hated in India. He had a low opinion of Indians, and call them "A beastly people with a beastly religion."